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**COMMUNICATION IN IMPLEMENTING SAFETY CULTURE ONBOARD
SEABOURN CRUISES AND THE LEVEL OF SATISFACTION OF CREW ON
BOARD: AN AUTOETHNOGRAPHIC STUDY**

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Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **SANDY JARAMILLA BAYAS** with the title: **“COMMUNICATION IN IMPLEMENTING SAFETY CULTURE ONBOARD SEABOURN CRUISES AND THE LEVEL OF SATISFACTION OF CREW ON BOARD: AN AUTOETHNOGRAPHIC STUDY”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Program.

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Biographical Sketch

Sandy Bayas stands as a seasoned seafarer with an illustrious career spanning nearly three decades in the cruise line industry, where he has honed his skills and contributed significantly as a stage and production manager. At the heart of his world, lies his cherished family; his wife, Filipina Bayas, serves as his steadfast partner, alongside their two daughters, Louise Anne and Sandra Anne, and their son, Sanders Phillippe Bayas, each adding joy and purpose to his life.

Sandy's academic foundation was laid at the prestigious Lyceum of the Philippines University, where he pursued and attained a degree in Mass Communication, with a specialization in broadcasting. This educational background not only equipped him with a diverse skill set but also instilled in him a profound understanding of communication dynamics, which have been instrumental in his professional role on the high seas.

Embarking on his journey in the maritime domain, Sandy has navigated through various challenges and experiences, each shaping him into a revered figure among his peers and subordinates. His role as a stage and production manager aboard a cruise line is not merely a job but a testament to his passion for the sea and commitment to excellence. Sandy's dedication to his craft and his ability to lead and inspire his team have been pivotal in delivering outstanding entertainment and productions, making every voyage memorable for passengers from across the globe.

Sandy Bayas's life is a narrative of dedication, resilience, and love, underscored by his unwavering commitment to his family and profession. As he continues to sail through the chapters of his life, his legacy as a seafarer and a family man remains an inspiration to many.

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Dedication

This study and work is especially dedicated to my wife Fina and my children Louise, Sandra and Sanders. They have been my source of inspiration accomplishing my studies until the finish line. Thank you for all your moral and loving family support encouraging me to keep on going at times I wanted to stop.

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Abstract

This study delves into the critical role of communication in cultivating a robust safety culture aboard Seabourn Cruises, and its subsequent impact on crew satisfaction. Employing an autoethnographic approach, the investigation analyzed thematic data from four participant narratives to derive meaningful insights. The research highlights the indispensable nature of direct and clear communication channels in maintaining safety standards and facilitating the swift dissemination of essential safety information. The study identifies benchmarking against industry standards as a crucial method for improving safety practices, with the approach to safety communication significantly influencing crew satisfaction levels. The establishment of trust in leadership and the active engagement of crew members in safety initiatives were pinpointed as key factors for the successful adoption of safety protocols. The necessity for ongoing enhancements in safety practices, supported by an effective feedback system, was emphasized to accommodate the dynamic nature of the maritime environment. The research also addresses communication challenges, such as the overload of non-essential emails, which can undermine safety efforts, and calls for the adoption of more streamlined communication strategies. Recommendations for maritime organizations, particularly Seabourn Cruises, include prioritizing straightforward communication, nurturing a trust-based culture through active feedback loops, aligning with industry best practices, and mitigating communication barriers to boost both safety and crew satisfaction.

Keywords: Communication, Safety Culture, Crew Satisfaction, Seabourn Cruises, Autoethnography, Maritime Safety, Feedback Loops.

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

The allure of cruising as a premium leisure activity has surged in recent years, with luxury liners offering unparalleled experiences that blend adventure, relaxation, and opulence (Meng et al., 2023). Amidst this burgeoning popularity, the imperative of ensuring the safety of passengers and crew alike has never been more pronounced. The maritime sector, especially within the luxury cruise domain, has increasingly emphasized the cultivation of a robust safety culture. Research by Hasanspahić et al. (2021) underscores the pivotal role human factors play in maritime safety, revealing that a considerable proportion of maritime mishaps are attributable to human errors rather than mechanical failures. This insight shifts the safety paradigm from a purely technical focus to one that encompasses human-centric approaches, spotlighting the critical importance of effective communication in bolstering maritime safety protocols.

The essence of effective communication in enacting organizational strategies is well-documented across various industries. O'Daniel (2008) sheds light on the dire consequences that communication breakdowns can entail, ranging from operational disruptions to grave safety risks, particularly in high-stakes environments like maritime operations. The complexity of establishing seamless communication is magnified on luxury cruise ships such as Seabourn Cruises, where the crew's diverse cultural and linguistic backgrounds present unique challenges to clear and cohesive interactions. Daniels (2017) highlights the potential safety hazards that can arise from such communication barriers, emphasizing the need for tailored strategies to bridge these gaps and foster a unified safety culture.

Moreover, the interconnection between crew satisfaction and their engagement with safety culture principles cannot be overstated. O'Daniel (2008) posits that a contented crew, proficient in effective communication, is more likely to adhere to safety protocols and respond adeptly in crises. This research delves into the criticality of efficacious communication in embedding a safety culture aboard Seabourn Cruises and examines how such communicative practices influence crew satisfaction. Through this lens, the study aims to unravel the nuances of communication as a linchpin in the successful implementation of safety measures and its ripple effects on the well-being and contentment of the crew.

Background of the Study

Over the past decade, the maritime industry has undergone significant changes and has been actively adapting to new circumstances. The field of shipping has experienced a multitude of transformations, ranging from advancements in technology to evolving patterns in global trade. Amid various concerns and considerations, the maritime industry strongly emphasizes cultivating a robust safety culture, particularly within the context of cruise ships. Robust safety measures are widely recognized as crucial for ensuring the well-being of both passengers and crew members. As per the International Maritime Organization (IMO), a comprehensive framework of maritime safety protocols has been universally implemented since 2018. These protocols encompass various measures, addressing both technical aspects and human-centered strategies (Raunek, 2021).

The concept of "effective communication" in implementing safety measures, particularly on luxury cruise liners such as Seabourn, emerges as a crucial area of focus. Lin et al. (2022) highlight cruise ship crews' diverse nationalities. Linguistic and cultural diversity in our global society clearly indicates our interconnectedness and

shared humanity. However, it also presents us with distinct communication obstacles we must navigate. This observation is supported by the findings of Buarqoub (2019). In a context characterized by miscommunication or misunderstanding, there exists the potential for significant consequences that can directly impede the successful establishment and integration of a safety culture.

Seabourn Cruises, a renowned name in luxury sailing, places great importance on upholding an exceptional safety record. This responsibility is closely linked to the dedication and comprehension of the crew members. The maritime industry has witnessed several incidents in the past that have served as poignant reminders of the inherent risks associated with inadequate communication practices. In their comprehensive investigation, an article published by SAFETY4SEA (2020) highlighted real-life examples to shed light on the underlying factors contributing to these incidents. Their findings revealed a significant correlation between communication breakdowns and such accidents, with incidents being attributed to communication.

Extensive research on safety culture and communication in various cruise ships is essential to comprehending and improving safety perceptions among travelers. The significance of safety in shaping an individual's intentions regarding cruise travel, especially during crisis situations, cannot be overstated (Mansfeld & Pizam, 2006). Safety perceptions, defined as the subjective sense of being protected against potential risks, have a significant impact on travelers' decisions (Sönmez & Graefe, 1998b). In fact, this perception of safety strongly influences travel preferences and choices for tourism products and services (Mansfeld & Pizam, 2006). It is evident from numerous studies that individuals' risk perceptions, whether related to health outbreaks, terrorist activities, or natural disasters, are closely associated with their

overall perceptions of safety and subsequent travel decisions (Floyd et al., 2004; Reynolds & Balinbin, 2003).

Furthermore, research indicates that safety perceptions play a mediating role in the relationship between risk perceptions and travel decisions (Liu et al., 2016; Reisinger & Mavondo, 2005). Liu et al. (2016) discovered that perceived safety mediated the link between risk perception attitudes and travel intentions, specifically in the context of political instability risks. Similarly, Reisinger and Mavondo (2005) found that safety perceptions mediated the relationship between motivations and intentions for international travel.

In conclusion, it is imperative to understand the safety culture and effective communication strategies within cruise ships to shape crew members perceptions and influence their decisions regarding cruise travel. Further research in this area is necessary to enhance safety practices and ensure a secure environment for cruise ship staff and crews.

Moreover, it is worth noting that a significant correlation exists between safety culture, effective communication, and the overall satisfaction of the crew members. According to the research conducted by An et al. (2023), it has been suggested that crew members provided with effective communication tools and clear guidelines demonstrate improved task performance and express higher levels of job satisfaction. Therefore, it is crucial to conduct a comprehensive analysis of the impact of effective communication on the safety culture aboard Seabourn Cruises and its subsequent influence on the overall satisfaction levels of the crew members.

Statement of the Problem

The researcher has been captivated by the intersection of personal experiences and broader cultural phenomena for a considerable duration. Being a crew member on Seabourn Cruises presently, the researcher's personal experiences have frequently intersected with the larger contexts of maritime safety and crew satisfaction. There is a gap in people's understanding of how personal narratives and collective experiences intersect, specifically regarding the importance of effective communication in fostering a safety culture onboard.

Through an autoethnographic approach, this study explored the intricate dynamics of effective communication in fostering a safety culture among crew members on Seabourn Cruises. Additionally, it sought to investigate the impact of this safety culture on the overall satisfaction levels of the crew.

This research study is grounded in the methodology of autoethnography, aimed to explore the complex dynamics of communication and safety culture on Seabourn Cruises. By examining the collective experiences of the crew members and juxtaposing them with individual personal narratives, this study gained a deeper understanding of the various layers involved in these aspects. The objective of this study is to provide a comprehensive analysis of maritime safety culture and its impact on crew satisfaction by utilizing narratives derived from the experiences and observations of seafarers.

1. What is the dynamics of communication between the deck (captains), engine (engineers), and hotel services in seabourn cruise?
2. What are the thoughts of the onboard crew members of Seabourn Cruise towards the culture of safety?

3. What are the effective communication approaches that contribute to the culture of safety of Seabourn Cruise?
4. In what manner can the strategic approach of effective communication be characterized when it comes to implementing safety culture onboard Seabourn Cruises?
5. What insights can be gained from my experiences as an on board crew of Seabourn Cruise Ship toward Communication and Safety Culture, and how do these experiences shed light on broader issues of Job Satisfaction and Culture of Safety in a Cruise Ship?

Objectives of the Study

This autoethnography research seeks to explore the dynamics of communication among different departments (deck, engine, and hotel services) on Seabourn Cruise ships, focusing on the crew's perceptions of safety culture and effective communication approaches. Additionally, it aims to gain insights from the researcher's experiences as an onboard crew member, relating to communication, safety culture, job satisfaction, and broader issues within the cruise ship industry.

Objectives:

1. Investigate the dynamics of communication between the deck (captains), engine (engineers), and hotel services departments on Seabourn Cruise ships.
2. Examine the thoughts and attitudes of onboard crew members towards the safety culture aboard Seabourn Cruise ships.
3. Identify effective communication approaches that contribute to the establishment and maintenance of a safety culture on Seabourn Cruise ships.

4. Characterize the strategic approach to effective communication in the implementation of safety culture onboard Seabourn Cruises.
5. Analyze the researcher's experiences as an onboard crew member of Seabourn Cruise ships, focusing on communication, safety culture, job satisfaction, and broader implications for the cruise ship industry.

Significance of the Study

The study titled "Communication in Implementing Safety Culture Onboard Seabourn Cruises and the Level of Satisfaction of Crew on Board: An Autoethnography Study" holds great importance for different groups involved in the maritime industry. The significance of this research can be comprehended in the following manner:

Improving Safety Protocols: By recognizing the significant impact of effective communication on establishing safety cultures, Seabourn Cruises and other similar organizations can gain valuable insights that will help them enhance and refine their safety protocols and strategies.

Crew Well-being and Satisfaction: By investigating the crew's level of satisfaction, this research can establish a direct connection between the crew's well-being and the way safety communication is conveyed. When the crew is content and fulfilled, they are much more inclined to carry out their responsibilities efficiently. This guarantees their own well-being and safeguards the passengers' safety.

Operational Efficiency: One of the key benefits of effective communication is its ability to minimize misunderstandings, errors, and inefficiencies. This study highlights the significance of clear and concise communication, which has the potential to bring about operational enhancements. As a result, it can contribute to smoother sailings and faster procedures onboard.

Training and Development: The findings from this study can play a crucial role in developing effective training programs for crew members. These programs emphasize the significance of effective communication in ensuring safety, ultimately resulting in a more prepared and capable crew.

Industry Benchmarking: This study can serve as a benchmark for the broader maritime industry. Companies have the opportunity to utilize these findings in order to assess and evaluate their own communication strategies and safety cultures, comparing them to the high standards established by Seabourn Cruises.

Passenger Confidence: Passenger safety and satisfaction lie at the core of the cruising experience. When it comes to ensuring passenger safety, effective communication plays a crucial role. By demonstrating a strong commitment to safety, airlines can instill confidence in their passengers, fostering brand loyalty and encouraging repeat business.

Policy Formulation: The findings of this study can be valuable for regulatory bodies in the maritime sector, as they can utilize the insights to develop or modify policies related to safety communications. Implementing this measure would guarantee a consistent and uniform approach to safety throughout the entire industry.

In essence, this study illuminates the crucial relationship between effective communication and safety onboard Seabourn Cruises. The ripple effect of its findings can influence a broad spectrum of practices, policies, and perceptions in the maritime domain.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Introduction

Maritime operations, with their vast oceans and intricate maneuvers, genuinely exemplify the complexity of logistics. Communication is the critical component that drives these operations, serving as the crucial element that ensures tasks are carried out seamlessly and potential risks are addressed proactively. Communication is crucial in this domain, and its importance cannot be overstated. Every ship, including high-end cruise liners like Seabourn Cruises, is a vibrant and complex system. The ability to communicate clearly and respond promptly can decide between smooth sailing and potentially disastrous situations (Fan, 2017).

Regarding the safety culture onboard, one must recognize the crucial role of effective communication. Effective communication channels are essential for safety protocols to maintain efficacy, even if they have been meticulously designed. According to James et al. (2018), the essence of maritime safety lies in adhering to rules and effective communication, both speaking and listening. Therefore, it is crucial to emphasize maintaining a harmonious relationship between communication and safety culture. This brings numerous benefits and plays a vital role in ensuring the overall well-being of the crew and passengers.

Safety Culture in Maritime Settings

In the maritime industry, safety culture refers to the collective values, behaviours, and beliefs shaping how people prioritize safety. It's all about how these elements interact within the organization's formal structure to establish a set of norms for safety Veiga (2002). This culture highlights the shared dedication, evident

across all levels of the organization, to prioritize safety as the utmost priority among all operational objectives. The importance of this ethos cannot be overstated in maritime settings. The risks involved in seafaring are significant; the operating environment is vast, and a complex network of human-machine interfaces is on board. When we take a moment to look back at past events, we gain valuable insights into just how important it is to have a strong culture of safety. One incident that stands out is the tragic Herald of Free Enterprise disaster in 1987. The tragic loss of 193 lives occurred due to a failure in communication and the disregard of safety protocols, ultimately leading to the ferry capsizing (Gill & Wahner, 2012). These tragic events highlight the importance of not only implementing strict safety protocols but also fostering a culture that values and follows them.

The maritime industry has come to acknowledge the utmost significance of fostering a safety culture over the years. Consequently, it has taken proactive measures to implement and establish best practices. These practices include ongoing training programs that empower crew members to freely express safety concerns without facing any negative consequences. Regular safety drills are also conducted, meticulous records are kept, and feedback loops are implemented to enhance protocols (Arslan et al., 2016). Nowadays, the emphasis is placed on taking proactive measures rather than relying solely on reactive solutions. This shift aims to guarantee that vessels operate by the most stringent safety standards.

The Phenomenal Growth of Cruising

The cruise industry has experienced remarkable growth, leading various cruise companies to commission the construction of new ships worldwide (European Cruise Council, 2010). While larger cruise lines focus on economies of scale and

target a broad demographic, Seabourn Cruises remains committed to offering a discerning clientele an intimate and refined experience (Ward, 2010). Approximately 15 to 20 million guests embarked on cruises globally in a single year, contributing to the industry's success (Ward, 2010). Also, Cruise tourism plays a vital role in the worldwide tourism sector and has been experiencing significant expansion. While it has been traditionally popular in the USA and Europe, China is also witnessing substantial growth in this industry (Hung et al., 2019).

Effective Communication: Theoretical Perspectives

Communication is the vital thread that weaves through countless organizational processes. Effective communication, at its essence, involves transmitting information in a way that is easily understood by the person receiving it. This means being clear concise, and ensuring the recipient comprehends the message. The ultimate goal is establishing mutual understanding between both parties (Fiske, 2018). Over the years, numerous models have been put forth to shed light on the intricate communication process. One example of a model that outlines the key components of communication is the Shannon-Weaver model. This model identifies the sender, message, channel, receiver, and feedback as the fundamental elements in any communication process (Shannon & Weaver, 1949). Although this model may seem simplified, it highlights the crucial role of both transmitting and receiving information to achieve effective communication.

Communication plays a crucial role in ensuring efficiency and safety within maritime settings. It is an indispensable aspect that cannot be overlooked. Effective communication is crucial for smooth operations, timely decision-making, and preventing misunderstandings that could cause problems or disasters. Effective

communication is crucial when sailing through dangerous waters or handling emergency situations on board a vessel. Maintaining clear and flawless communication to guarantee the safety of the crew members and the ship itself (Korczyk, 2016).

On the other hand, when it comes to cruise ships, the diverse and vibrant atmospheres they offer can sometimes pose challenges when it comes to effective communication. The diverse mix of crew members from different nationalities, languages, and cultures can sometimes result in misinterpretations or misunderstandings (Galešić & Coslovich, 2019). For example, a simple word or gesture considered harmless in one culture could easily be interpreted as offensive in another culture. In addition, the intense and demanding atmosphere aboard the ship, where crew members frequently put in extended hours, can worsen communication breakdowns. The presence of different hierarchical structures introduces an additional level of complexity. This could discourage open communication, as individuals may fear facing consequences or hesitate to exceed their designated roles.

Safety Culture and Effective Communication: The Symbiotic Relationship

Safety culture and effective communication in maritime settings are deeply intertwined. A strong safety culture depends significantly on effective communication strategies. This is because clear understanding, consistent implementation, and ongoing improvement of safety procedures are all ensured through effective communication.

Communication is crucial in implementing safety procedures, and this influence can be observed at different levels. Effective communication plays a

crucial role in ensuring the safety of a ship, from the top management who develop safety protocols to the crew members who implement them on the deck. It is not enough for the crew to understand these protocols; they must also internalize them to ensure their effectiveness. This practice's main purpose is to ensure a consistent alignment between what is perceived as safe and what is actually practiced as safe on board.

Take, for example, the Exxon Valdez oil spill in 1989. This unfortunate incident stands as a stark reminder of the consequences that can arise from breakdowns in communication. A combination of factors caused the disaster, but a significant one was the lack of clear communication between the crew and the captain regarding navigation instructions. This miscommunication ultimately resulted in the ship running aground, triggering one of the worst environmental disasters ever seen in maritime history (Williams & Treadaway, 1992).

On the other hand, let's look at the 'Miracle on the Hudson' that occurred in 2009. Although it was indeed an aviation incident, it serves as a powerful reminder of just how crucial effective communication can be when saving lives. Captain Sully Sullenberger and his crew demonstrated exceptional communication skills, which were instrumental in successfully landing the aircraft on the Hudson River and saving the lives of all 155 people on board (Sullenberger, 2013).

Although they come from different areas, both of these incidents highlight how crucial effective communication is in times of crisis and how it can directly impact safety results. Safety culture and communication cannot be emphasized enough, whether in preventing disasters or ensuring that everyday safety protocols are

adhered to. These two aspects have a mutually beneficial relationship crucial for maintaining a safe environment.

Crew Satisfaction: A Function of Safety and Communication

The crew's satisfaction within maritime operations is a crucial measure beyond just the workforce's happiness. A cohesive and well-functioning operation is typically characterized by a careful balance between efficiency and the safety and well-being of its crew members.

The significance of ensuring crew satisfaction in maritime operations cannot be overstated. It is crucial to prioritize the well-being and contentment of the crew members on board. A satisfied crew is likelier to perform their duties efficiently and effectively, leading to smoother and safer maritime operations. Crew satisfaction plays a vital role in maintaining a positive work environment.

The crew's satisfaction in maritime settings directly impacts a voyage's productivity, efficiency, and overall success (Nielsen et al., 2013). When the crew is content, they tend to be more involved and dedicated, resulting in fewer errors, improved compliance with safety procedures, and a more enjoyable atmosphere. These factors are essential for long journeys.

Truly effective communication can foster a deep sense of belonging and worth within a team of individuals. According to McAfee et al., (1995), when crew members perceive that their opinions are valued and their concerns are promptly attended to, there is an increase in job satisfaction levels. Directly, it has the potential to result in quicker problem resolution, enhanced comprehension of tasks, and a reduced likelihood of mishaps occurring. Enhancing communication in an indirect

manner can have numerous positive outcomes. It cultivates trust among individuals, mitigates any sense of isolation or misinformation, and fosters a sense of unity within a crew. Ultimately, these factors collectively contribute to heightened satisfaction levels.

Maritime operations emphasize safety, as it is crucial for the actual execution of tasks and the crew's perception of their well-being. According to Larsen et al. (2012), job satisfaction tends to be higher when crew members perceive their environment as safe. Communication plays a crucial role in connecting the perception of safety with the reality of safety. Boosting crew members' confidence and satisfaction is closely linked to clear communication of safety procedures and the presence of feedback mechanisms. When these aspects are effectively implemented, crew members' perceptions align more closely with the actual safety conditions, positively impacting their overall confidence and satisfaction levels.

To sum up, the interdependent connection among crew contentment, security, and effective communication is readily apparent in maritime operations. To ensure the safety and satisfaction of their crew members, maritime operators must prioritize fostering open, clear, and regular communication channels. Effective communication plays a pivotal role in achieving this goal.

Multicultural Challenges in Communication aboard Cruise Ships

Cruise ships offer a distinctive setting where work and leisure intertwine within the confined space of a vessel. This complexity is further heightened by the diverse multicultural makeup of the crew. On board, effective communication becomes both a challenge and a necessity as crew members from diverse corners of the globe bring along their unique cultures, languages, and communication styles.

The crew members on board exhibit a remarkable diversity when it comes to their nationality, language, and culture.

Cruise ships have gained a reputation for their remarkable crew composition, which frequently consists of individuals hailing from numerous countries across the globe (Borodzicz & Gibson, 2006). The presence of diversity on board not only enhances the overall experience but also introduces a wide range of languages, cultural norms, values, and communication styles. The variations in perspectives can be advantageous as they offer a wide range of insights. However, they can also pose a challenge when it comes to effectively communicating safety and operational messages to everyone.

Language barriers and cultural differences can lead to significant misunderstandings, which can have serious consequences. In some cultures, acknowledging a lack of comprehension regarding a directive could potentially be perceived as a display of vulnerability or inadequacy. This perception has the potential to cause crew members to perform tasks based on assumptions rather than a clear understanding. Consequently, this can result in operational errors or, in more severe cases, safety incidents (Kahveci, 2007). Moreover, it is worth noting that certain cultures often employ indirect communication styles, which can potentially be misunderstood by individuals accustomed to more direct forms of communication. This can result in confusion or a perception of evasiveness.

Maritime organizations have implemented various strategies to effectively address and overcome the challenges they face. These strategies encompass a range of approaches that aim to enhance operational efficiency, ensure safety, and promote sustainability in the maritime industry. One of the key strategies adopted by

maritime organizations is the implementation of advanced technologies. This includes the use of automated systems, such as autonomous vessels and drones, to streamline operations and reduce human error.

Maritime organizations, fully aware of the significance of effective communication in the midst of such a wide range of diversity, have implemented various strategies (Noble et al., 2011):

- Language Standardization: English is commonly chosen as the primary language used on board, and crew members are expected to possess a certain level of proficiency in this language (Mönnigmann & Čulić-Viskota, 2017).
- Cross-cultural training workshops are incredibly valuable as they teach crew members about diverse cultures, communication styles, and effective strategies for resolving misunderstandings (Dalsky & Landis, 2013).
- Cultural Celebration: We create an environment that embraces diversity by fostering a sense of mutual respect and understanding through the celebration of various cultural events and encouraging crew members to share their traditions (Clermont et al., 1993).
- Visual Aids and Demonstrations: Incorporating visual methods of instruction or demonstrations can often overcome language barriers, guaranteeing comprehension and accurate replication of tasks (Sperotto, 2016).

Multicultural challenges in communication on cruise ships cannot be ignored. However, these challenges can be successfully addressed with appropriate strategies, resulting in improved operational efficiency and the overall welfare of all individuals on board.

The cruise industry supports over one million jobs and more than \$150 billion in annual global activity. (Cruise Lines International Association, 2021, as cited in Sharples et al., 2022). Communication is vital to business, especially during times of uncertainty (Sharples et al., 2022).

The research of Sharples et al (2022) stated that clear messaging within one business inspires stakeholders to bet on the business since they will be updated even in times of uncertainty. Furthermore, it explored the communication crisis in cruise ships during the pandemic, applying the construal level theory. The CLT is defined as the psychological distance between a person's capabilities and the behavior of an incoming event (Liberman et al., 2007, as cited in Sharples et al., 2022). This theory defines the communication effectiveness within one company depending on the situations being tackled. Sharples et al. (2022) used an empirical research design to understand the marketing side of cruise ships and the struggles and fears during those trying times for consumers of the service themselves. The study ended by emphasizing abstract-focused communication to avoid customer cancellation after booking and providing confidence during the Pandemic (Sharples et al., 2022).

The Internet and Information and Communications Technology widely changed the face of tourism around the world (Vafeidou, 2019, as cited in Ho & Lee, 2007 and Neuhofer et al., 2012).

The Master study written by Vafeidou (2019) covers different aspects of Communication Technologies concerning the vast elements of experiences felt by cruisers in the Cruising Industry; this study's primary goal is to explore the possible improvement of cruisers' experiences through the help of ever-growing ICT and

Smart Tourism according to Vafeidou (2019). The study ended by discussing the changes between the older types of cruising and Smart Cruising, wherein the latter involves the cruisers, stakeholders, and crew members, and the advancement of technologies creates a whole new kind of cruising experience. The service experiences that cruisers actively co-create result in positive value outputs for them, other cruisers, and even the company. The conclusion showed the Cruise companies taking advantage of the latest technology that may help the cruise ship experience a higher standard of enjoyment. (Vafeidou. 2019)

Another work from (Sharples et al.,2019) suggested that communication within cruise ships is essential. This study focused on managing the Cruise Industry crisis using internal communications to help the workforce become resilient. The study used a theoretical application of the Regulatory Focus theory to internal communication, applying both prevention and promotion-focused messages in making a resilient team.

The efficacy and efficiency of communication differ among cultures due to elements including act, scene, agent, agency, purpose, and technique. This could be observed in multi-race companies such as the cruise and ship industry (Nuryana et al.,2018). This study examines Indonesian and Dutch crew communication at Holland America Line using a qualitative method, focusing on their social conditions and experiences. The study criticizes the positivistic approach, which views individuals as passive, and the phenomenological approach, which views individuals as active (Mulyana and Rachmat, 2000: 155, as cited in Nuryana et al., 2018). Gudykunst and Kim emphasize that strangers adapt to host society by detecting similarities and differences and forming personal connections. (Gudykunst& Kim, 1992, as cited in Nuryana et.al, 2018) The study concluded that interactions between

the European and Indonesian crew members on Holland America Line cruise ships have been positive since the 1970s. Indonesian sailors have assimilated Dutch traditions, partaking in European rituals, and speaking their home tongue. The European crew community, especially in the Netherlands, has become fluent in Indonesian and eats Indonesian cuisine. This amicable connection makes significant improvements in understanding and communication possible, which lowers the likelihood of problems aboard cruise ships (Nuryana et al., 2018).

According to a blog post by Crew-Center (2023), the crew members created jargon on board the ship to improve communication and foster a sense of oneness among themselves. The crew of the ship has created an extraordinary language for intercommunication. For instance, if the person taking our place during the dinner break is 20 minutes late, we would say, "You give me a hard timem, maaaaan.". It also concerns defending neighborhood businesses against supervisors who give employees more flexible scheduling. When anything is described as done "Rambo style," it generally alludes to quickly and carelessly. This is one of the words the ship's crew uses the most (Crew-Center, 2023).

Safety is not limited to those who work at Cruise Lines; even avid customers are also connected to these safety measures. A study conducted by Liu-Lastres in 2018 covers the responses of cruise line customers to risk and crisis communication. The study focused on the Norovirus that usually causes gastroenteritis in the US. (CDC, 2017, as cited in Liu-Lastres et al., 2018) Two hundred forty responses were examined using the framework for risk perception and attitude. Results indicated that safety perceptions and group differences in outcome factors moderated the link between RPAs and intentions to take a cruise. The study emphasizes the need for additional empirical research on crisis communication in tourism. The cruise industry

should inform travelers about the norovirus and other diseases, such as influenza, to encourage interest in cruising. The VSP program, which only covers GI disorders, should be expanded to foreign countries. Ports and foreign countries. The sector ought to think about making this program available to non-American ships. (Liu-Lastres et. al., 2018)

In an article written by Yates in 2022, the cruising industry is booming with travelers of all ages and socioeconomic levels using onboard communication; the cruise business is developing. According to Wireless Maritime Services (WMS) president and CEO Pramod Arora, cruise lines should develop a customer-focused product and communication ecosystem that allows passengers to select the best plan for their connectivity requirements. With this, any passenger of any age can pick the right plan for them. Through cellular and Wi-Fi services, cruise companies can now provide connectivity packages that are more adaptable, specialized, and efficient. In order to ensure that passengers receive the services they desire, increase penetration and usage, and boost guest satisfaction, according to Arora, cruise companies must modify their marketing and pricing strategies. (Yates, 2022) Based on the article, the cruising industry is not only adjusting to the state of the world now, but it is also adjusting its communication capabilities to enhance customer care and crew efficiency (Yates, 2022).

Seabourn Cruises: An Overview

Seabourn Cruise Line was established in 1988, under the leadership of Knut Kloster, a prominent Norwegian shipping magnate. The company's headquarters are located in Seattle, Washington. It operates a fleet of six small ships that provide

itineraries to various destinations across the globe (*All-Inclusive Ultra-Luxury Award Winning Cruises | Seabourn, n.d.*).

Seabourn's ships have gained a reputation for their generously proportioned accommodations, exceptional dining experiences, and unwavering commitment to attentive service. The line also provides a diverse range of onboard activities and amenities, including spa treatments, fitness classes, and enrichment lectures (*All-Inclusive Ultra-Luxury Award Winning Cruises | Seabourn, n.d.*).

Operational Scale

Seabourn Cruise Line operates a fleet of six ships: Seabourn Odyssey, Seabourn Sojourn cruise ship, Seabourn Quest Cruise Ship, Seabourn Encore Cruise Ship, Seabourn Ovation Cruise Ship, and Seabourn Venture cruise ship. The ships range in size from 458 to 600 guests and offer a variety of itineraries to destinations around the world (Wikipedia contributors, 2023)..

Communication and Safety Protocols

Seabourn Cruise Line has a comprehensive set of communication and safety protocols in place. These protocols are designed to ensure the safety and well-being of guests and crew members (Wikipedia contributors, 2023).

The company's communication protocols include:

- A dedicated 24/7 call center
- A fleet-wide emergency communication system
- A system for tracking guests and crew members

The company's safety protocols include:

- A rigorous safety training program for all crew members

- A system of redundancies for critical systems
- A comprehensive disaster plan

Seabourn Cruise Line is a member of the Cruise Lines International Association (CLIA), which has a set of safety standards that all member lines must adhere to. In addition to its safety protocols, Seabourn Cruise Line complies with all applicable international and national regulations (*Cruising home*, n.d.).

Communication for Safety Measures

Safety Challenges

The cruise industry faces common safety challenges, necessitating compliance with regulations set by the International Maritime Organization, USPH, and individual company safety management systems (Roberts, 2002). Communication barriers often contribute to accidents and incidents onboard, underscoring the critical role of effective communication in ensuring safety (Roberts, 2002). While technological advancements aim to enhance safety, it is crucial for operators to comprehend and effectively communicate these advancements to their coworkers (Roberts, 2002).

Safety Initiatives

Cruise lines have developed comprehensive safety management systems to adhere to maritime laws, as accidents and injuries can have severe consequences for both crew members and passengers (Ren et al., 2008). Tragic incidents such as the Costa Concordia disaster highlight the importance of a robust safety culture and effective communication protocols (Hooper, 2012). Seabourn Cruises recognizes the significance of safety behavior and fosters a safety culture through regular safety

meetings, drills, and empowering crew members to take ownership of safety concerns (Griffin & Neal, 2000; Mearns et al., 2003).

Safety as an Essential Culture

Seabourn Cruises places safety as an integral part of its company culture, conducting regular internal and external audits to assess safety procedures and identify areas for improvement (Griffin & Neal, 2000). The company empowers its officers, staff, and crew to actively contribute to safety, promoting a supportive and collaborative environment where everyone's well-being is paramount (Geller, 1998). Communication materials such as posters and newsletters serve as important tools to promote safety awareness and encourage crew members to voice concerns and report any issues (Geller, 1998). By fostering open and honest communication, Seabourn Cruises aims to maintain a safe and productive working environment for all crew members.

Safety Culture in Cruise Ships

In a blog article written by Capt. Jassal, in 2020, it was stated that safety culture is the environment of the ship's staff performing each task with the required safety measure even when the faster option is more accessible. In addition, Jassal (2020) gave an example by giving a real-life situation wherein personnel must follow the captain's order to come to the deck, but the personnel need to be wearing safety gear. Jassal (2020) stated that going directly to the deck is much easier and less hassle, and getting ready with your gear is much more work. The author asked, "Are you willing to trade off your inconvenience for safety?" The captain stated multiple real-life examples in the article stating the extreme importance of safety culture in a company and how it will affect the workflow within the ship. (Jassal,2020)

According to Hipol (2023), several factors pose risks to a company's safety culture: human performance, state fatigue, the shortage of human resources on board, the rapid development of technology, and some social pressure from the companies. In Hipol's study, the author provided a diagram of factors contributing to safety culture. The diagram was divided into three major sections: competence, professionalism, and communication. These sections were divided into subcategories to further explain the points needed for a thriving safety culture. The author determined through this study the crucial role that education plays in improving the safety culture on board. Due to the high-risk environment, seamen confront while at sea, a job in seafaring is physically and emotionally demanding. (Hipol, 2023)

However, some characteristics and attitudes of the human element, who are reluctant to speak out and be forceful regarding safety, might endanger safety. However, according to the participants, education and training can improve a want-to attitude toward safety, as the MAAP education and training program reportedly did (Hipol, 2023).

An influential safety culture is a mix of leadership and commitment from the leaders, along with effective two-way communication between leaders and employees (Predovan & Čulin, 2017, p. 122). This study focused on the role of the Master in Safety Culture improvements onboard ships. It was concluded that safety culture in a ship is critical; however, no matter how hard companies strive to improve the safety culture within their ships, barriers, and challenges are present to achieve a completely full-proof safety culture. The safety culture on board ships is influenced by the masters' leadership qualities and accompanying behaviors, which may reduce risk factors (Predovan and Čulin, 2017).

The UNESCAP (United Nations Economic and Social Commission for Asia and the Pacific) did thorough research on improving Maritime Transport Safety in the ESCAP region in 2016. The study focused on the importance of Maritime transportation and how safety culture could be improved in different sectors. According to Chartier et al. (2016), the maritime industry is the primary source of transporting goods and people, whether long-distance or short-transfer. The study used a survey covering the ESCAP region. There was a rise in demand for ferry transport, especially on cruise ships, starting in 2016. In the data presented in the study, human error is the leading cause of many ship accidents, sizing up from 61 percent to 85 percent. However, there are a lot of different risks provided in the study, and a master plan for maritime safety is needed and will be used as a guideline for the ESCAP members. The study finally concluded with a Master Safety plan that could help countries, especially developing countries, reduce human error risk (Chartier et al., 2016).

Most goods transport lies in the shipping industry, up to 90 percent (Kirwan et al., 2020). The funded study focused on the safety learning culture of the shipping industry, talking about the collection of accident interviews regarding shipping safety. The study provided eight (8) sections of verbatim interviews, providing a wide array of understandings of safety learning and safety culture. These eight are investigation, reporting, near-miss reporting, understanding the human element, ship safety, safety management systems, just culture, and safety learning. Using these elements, the study proposed safety learning approaches to enhance safety culture within a vessel. The study primarily promoted the difference between safety culture and safety learning culture using set interviews with different ship personnel and companies, wherein the latter is not only following set structures and

cooperating to ensure safety, but it is the mindset shared within an organization until it becomes a reflex (Kirwan et al., 2020).

In a study by Radic et al. 2020, the safety of the cruise ship workers' work assurance was also at risk due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The Cruise Line International Association (CLIA) halted cruise ship operations, which led to a No Sail Order from the CDC. As a result, 1.17 million jobs globally are in danger, and significant cruise companies suffer financial difficulties. Norwegian Cruise Line Holdings Ltd., Royal Caribbean Cruises Ltd., and Carnival Corporation laid off or sidelined workers. (Radic et al., 2020) This study examines worries, fears, sleep issues, a lack of social cohesiveness, perceived stress, and feelings of hope and belonging to determine the psychological impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on cruise ship staff. The findings provide significant contributions to the cruise tourism hypothesis. The research is exploratory since the authors were still finding out about the extent of the COVID-19 virus. An inductive method and a qualitative collection were used in online focus groups to find that the COVID-19 pandemic has erased joy and exposed flaws in the company's crisis management, contingency plans, and human resource management, dehumanizing cruise ship crew members (Radic et al., 2020).

Obstacles in Safety Communication

Effective communication plays a vital role in overcoming barriers to safety communication, such as language barriers, lack of attention to detail, unclear instructions, discrimination, and poor decision-making (Cole, 2000). Clear and impactful safety messages must be delivered with supporting evidence to ensure their effectiveness (Cole, 2000).

Language and Feedback

Onboard Seabourn Cruises, English serves as the official language, and crew members are required to communicate in English at all times (Hale, 2003). Constructive feedback, rather than subjective comments, is encouraged to promote safe behaviors and prevent accidents (Hale, 2003). Face-to-face communication and open dialogue are prioritized over electronic communication methods, fostering positive and healthy conversations, especially when addressing sensitive or conflicting matters (Hale, 2003). Weekly safety training sessions and evaluations further enhance communication and ensure continuous improvement in crew satisfaction (Håvold & Nettet, 2009; Mearns & Reader, 2008).

Embracing Change

Introducing changes onboard can face resistance, but clear and concise communication, coupled with positive language, helps facilitate acceptance and cooperation (Geller, 1996, 1998; Rivers, 2007). Seabourn Cruises adapted its safety measures during the pandemic, implementing changes such as mandatory face mask usage, quarantine protocols, and modified meal arrangements, which were effectively communicated to the crew members through the ship's safety site (Rivers, 2007). Proper communication and information dissemination played a crucial role in successfully implementing these changes.

Open and Closed Questions

Questioning is a vital communication skill that aids in gathering information, developing insights, and enhancing understanding (Geller, 1998). Onboard Seabourn Cruises, open-ended questions are used to engage crew members in

safety discussions and assessments, allowing for in-depth responses and eliciting their opinions and knowledge (Geller, 1998). Closed-ended questions, on the other hand, help gauge crew members' understanding of safety policies and their ability to apply their knowledge in real-life scenarios.

Job Satisfaction in Cruise Ship

Job satisfaction plays an essential role in every organization that has an employee. According to Maulabaksh and Rasik (2015), as cited in Sharma and Gupta, 2020), employees are work resources that any company should invest in. Also, employees excel in activities that grant long-term development, immediate gratification, fair compensation, and delivering superior value (Maidani, 1991, as cited in Sharma and Gupta, 2020). The study that Sharma and Gupta conducted compared employees' job satisfaction levels in different workplaces. The study analyzed the satisfaction level of 140 employees in seven industries using a questionnaire. The survey focused on healthcare, education, travel and tourism, outsourcing, education, healthcare, and logistics as it examined work satisfaction levels across seven industries. The results indicate that the healthcare and education sectors have the highest levels of work satisfaction, followed by travel, tourism, and education. The homogenous character of the outsourcing and insurance businesses exacerbates dissatisfaction. Business leaders can use these findings to create human resource policies to attract better candidates and boost productivity (Sharma & Gupta, 2020)

The cruise industry is the fastest-growing industry due to globalization and the high demand for tourism. (Cruise Lines International Association, 2020, as cited in Scherbl. 2020) Since there is a high demand for tourism and the cruising industry

is vastly growing, Scherbl (2020) focused on Improving Employee Retention Rates in the Cruise Industry by Assessing Living and Working Conditions since it was the problem based on recent studies that the cruise workforce is sixty-thousand (60,000) short while the workload will need two hundred-fifty thousand (250,000) by the end of 2020. (Cruise Industry News, 2018, as cited in Scherbl. 2020). The workload on board is very straining for the staff since the environment of the cruise revolves around its employees. Since there is a shortage of workers, but demand is rising, working conditions could be more stable since workers are expected to provide the same service with less help and sometimes work even more than the crew can handle (Sevcikova, 2011, as cited in Scherbl, 2020). In order to find out the job satisfaction rating of cruise ship workers, the study used a survey that was changed according to the needs of the study. Jinlin Zhao and Cherly Charter first used the survey, considered the most accurate for job satisfaction surveys (Zhao, 2003, as cited in Scherbl, 2020). The study ended with a discussion of the results, which was moderately satisfied with the current work. However, the profiles of the respondents changed the other aspects of satisfaction, starting from management to crew members.

In a study conducted by Hult et al. back in 2020, hardships encountered working at sea are a lot harder to deal with compared with the problems on land since they include homesickness and continuous "emotional labor," according to Hochschild, 1983, as cited in Hult et al., 2020, which talks about the round the clock interactions of crew members with the customers and cruisers that the crew members could not get any emotional rest from. Hult and colleagues' focal point in this study is to compare the pattern of organizational commitment and job satisfaction, which will soon be used as an analysis of theoretical applications of the

shipping industry. (Hult et al.,2020) . The team used surveys as a way of collecting data for the Swedish Register of Seafarers. The study also highlighted the difference between ships carrying passengers and cargo. Service ratings and senior deck officers—particularly service officers—have much greater organizational commitment levels on passenger ships. This could result from an increased sense of duty toward the other passengers. Some officers on the passenger ships depend on their job loyalty for job satisfaction (Hult et al., 2020).

In line with job satisfaction on cruise ships is customer satisfaction as well, and this is the focal point of Yoon and Cha's study back in 2020. Since 1990, cruise travel has considerably increased, with ocean cruises in Asia reaching a record high. However, the sector must address issues with corporate social responsibility and environmental effects. (Yoon and Cha, 2020) The study differentiated three (3) cruise lines within Asia regarding service quality. The study evaluates Costa Victoria, Diamond Princess, and Superstar Virgo in Asia, analyzing cruise SERVQUAL, consumer factors, and practical implications. The highest SERVQUAL rating among cruise ships is held by the Diamond Princess, demonstrating the necessity for regular inspections, quality service management, and investments in mega-ships to address mass family travel trends and customer distrust. The study suggests considering service quality while planning cruise ship navigation, emphasizing inspection, improvement, and overall operation. After COVID-19, travelers favor unhurried travel, prioritizing quality and genuine local experiences over quantity. Due to the need for economic advantages, a lighter infrastructure, eco-friendly small ships, regional mobility, and transportation resilience, the cruise industry may shift from mass cruises to niche cruises. This study proved the need for higher

satisfaction for workers to satisfy the cruisers' skeptical needs (Yoon and Cha, 2020).

Also, nowadays, job satisfaction is directly related to work-life balance. In research by Senando (2021), the study evaluated the work-life balance of the crew members of International Cruises, paying particular attention to their demographics, emotional and behavioral profiles, and work-life conflict. Most respondents were unmarried, female, college graduates, and employed for one to ten years. The report emphasized the significance of maintaining a healthy work-life balance, offering competitive pay and benefits, and implementing family care benefits policies. The recommendations include benefits for close family members, leniency for crew members with minor health difficulties, and solutions for workload and exhaustion problems. (Senando, 2021) The study concluded that cruise line companies could offer crew members advantages such as insurance coverage, paying for immediate family members, hiring crew members with minor health difficulties, and assistance with workload and exhaustion issues. They may also consider adding more crew members and reducing long shifts. Reinforcement mechanisms for quality of life may be implemented to encourage work-life balance (Senando, 2021).

Job satisfaction is sought in any profession and any nationality. Messina (2018) focused on the Job Satisfaction of deck officers, mainly Italians and Finnish deck workers on cruise ships. The thesis aims to investigate the characteristics that make a ship a desirable place to work by looking at the job satisfaction of Italian and Finnish deck officers. The study of Messina uses in-depth interviews with sailors between the ages of 31 and 61 to better understand their perspectives on life at sea. According to the definition of "job satisfaction," it is the inner fulfillment and sense of pride attained while completing a specific profession. This shows seafaring draws

people and improves their general well-being (Wicker, 2011, as cited in Messina, 2018). The study concluded that sea deck officers, cyclical work, a competitive income, and fascinating coworkers are all desirable elements that encourage motivation, career chances, and a happy work atmosphere (Messina, 2018).

Filipinos are one of the nationalities that dwell in the marine industry. The study by Asis-Castro and Edralin (2022) looks into the job satisfaction, active work engagement, dispositional effect, and flourishing components of Filipino seafarers' happiness at work in a maritime company. The study highlights the most critical aspects of workplace happiness and creates a new model to better understand the variables affecting employee and workplace satisfaction. The study used the Broaden and Build theory by Fredrickson (2004, as cited in Asis-Castro and Edralin, 2022), which tackles the positive emotions that play a crucial role in human life, fostering happiness, well-being, and flourishing. (Asis-Castro and Edralin, 2022) The study also used the Fisher model, which entails positive attitudes towards work. The study found that Filipino seafarers, including Cadets aged 36–42, reported work satisfaction. The study found that Filipino psychology influences attitudes and behaviors, affecting seafarers' happiness in the workplace. Vigorous work engagement, dispositional affect, flourishing at work, and job satisfaction explained 53% of the variance, while job satisfaction had no significant effect. These results may provide significant factors separating job satisfaction from other employee drives to work (Asis-Castro & Edralin, 2022). *Relationship with Ship Management*

The satisfaction of Seabourn Cruises' employees is strongly influenced by their relationship with ship management, which prioritizes effective communication and maintains an open-door policy (Hale, 2003). A supportive environment, where crew members are treated equally regardless of nationality, fosters job satisfaction

and contributes to the company's success (Hale, 2003). The implementation of a buddy system further enhances the support network for newly hired crew members (Håvold & Nettet, 2009; K. Mearns & Reader, 2008).

Nationality and Education

Seabourn Cruises employs individuals from various nationalities, fostering a diverse and inclusive work environment (Klein, 2002). While management positions often require higher levels of education and are predominantly filled by Europeans, South Africans, and North Americans, crew positions in the Hotel Department encompass a mix of nationalities, including Asians (Klein, 2002). Respect for one another, regardless of position or nationality, is emphasized to ensure a harmonious and safe working environment (Klein, 2002).

Work Environment

Seabourn Cruises adheres to maritime safety standards and continually strives to achieve a zero-accident policy (ILO, 2006). The company prioritizes safety procedures and provides a conducive work environment with proper safety protocols and personal protective equipment, fostering job satisfaction among crew members (ILO, 2006). By instilling a culture of safety and continuous improvement, Seabourn Cruises aims to create a positive and fulfilling work environment for all.

Communication Theory

One communication theory that is particularly relevant to the research entitled "Communication in Implementing Safety Culture Onboard Seabourn Cruises and the Level of Satisfaction of Crew on Board: An Autoethnography Study" is the Social Penetration Theory. Developed by Irwin Altman and Dalmis Taylor in 1973, this

theory suggests that as individuals engage in communication, their relationships deepen and evolve over time through self-disclosure and the sharing of personal information.

In the specific context of Seabourn Cruises, effective communication plays a crucial role in fostering a robust safety culture and enhancing crew satisfaction. By encouraging open and transparent communication channels, such as safety meetings, drills, and feedback sessions, the Social Penetration Theory can facilitate the development of trust, relationship-building, and effective collaboration among crew members. Through the process of self-disclosure and the exchange of safety-related information, crew members can deepen their understanding of safety protocols, identify potential hazards, and actively contribute to creating a safer working environment.

Furthermore, the theory highlights the significance of ongoing and reciprocal communication. As crew members engage in regular dialogue, they have the opportunity to share their concerns, provide feedback, and offer suggestions for improvement. This continuous communication process fosters the development of a shared safety culture onboard Seabourn Cruises, where all individuals feel empowered to take ownership of safety and actively contribute to the well-being of themselves and their fellow crew members.

By applying the principles of the Social Penetration Theory, Seabourn Cruises can create a communication environment that promotes safety, satisfaction, and collaboration among its crew members. The theory's focus on self-disclosure, trust-building, and continuous communication aligns closely with the objectives of the research, offering valuable insights into the role of effective communication in

implementing safety culture and enhancing crew satisfaction onboard Seabourn Cruises.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this research delves into the interplay between effective communication, safety culture, and crew satisfaction onboard Seabourn Cruises. It consists of three key components: Communication Strategies, Safety Culture, and Crew Satisfaction.

Communication Strategies:

This component focuses on the various communication strategies employed onboard Seabourn Cruises to ensure effective communication regarding safety. It encompasses both formal and informal channels such as safety meetings, drills, manuals, checklists, publications, and feedback systems. These strategies facilitate the exchange of safety information, promote open dialogue, and disseminate safety protocols among crew members.

Safety Culture

The safety culture component examines the shared values, beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors pertaining to safety onboard Seabourn Cruises. It encompasses the commitment of the company, management, and crew members to prioritize safety, comply with safety regulations, and engage in safety-related activities. A strong safety culture fosters a proactive approach to safety, encourages incident reporting and learning from near misses, and emphasizes continuous improvement in safety practices.

Crew Satisfaction:

Crew satisfaction is a crucial outcome influenced by effective communication and safety culture. This component considers the perceptions, experiences, and overall satisfaction of crew members with their working environment, safety measures, and communication practices. It encompasses factors such as job satisfaction, morale, engagement, and the sense of empowerment and involvement in safety-related decision-making processes.

The conceptual framework illustrates the interconnectedness of these components. Effective communication strategies facilitate the establishment and maintenance of a robust safety culture, which, in turn, contributes to higher levels of crew satisfaction. It recognizes that communication plays a critical role in shaping safety culture, and a positive safety culture is instrumental in enhancing crew satisfaction.

Through the utilization of an autoethnographic research approach, this study aims to explore the lived experiences and personal narratives of crew members,

shedding light on the complex dynamics between effective communication, safety culture, and crew satisfaction. The conceptual framework provides a theoretical foundation to guide data analysis and interpretation, ultimately contributing to a comprehensive understanding of the role of effective communication in implementing safety culture and enhancing crew satisfaction onboard Seabourn Cruises.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research methodology for studying "Communication in Implementing Safety Culture Onboard Seabourn Cruises and the Level of Satisfaction of Crew on Board: An Autoethnography Study" "This design allows for a deeper exploration of the personal experiences and narratives of crew members on Seabourn Cruises, shedding light on the impact of effective communication on safety culture and crew satisfaction.

This study employed a qualitative approach via an auto-ethnographic approach through an in-depth interview, given the exploratory nature of the objectives of this research. Qualitative research is defined as the process of organizing data into categories and identifying patterns among it. This definition implies that data and meaning emerge organically from the research context under a combination of observations, interviews, and document reviews, which emphasizes the importance of variables being studied in the context in which they are found (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

The lack of recent studies in relation to the role of effective communication in Implementing Safety Culture Onboard Seabourn Cruises and Crew Satisfaction makes qualitative, in-depth interviews an essential approach to providing extensive exploration of the present thoughts, beliefs, attitudes, work experiences, and knowledge of the onboard crews of cruise ship officers. Further, qualitative, in-depth interviews were also used in exploring past and unique experiences. As such, using a more effective and less structured in-depth interview helps uncover more detailed in-depth information than other data collection methods. It is suggested that a semi-

structured, in-depth interview is very useful if it leads to a form of simple conversation, making it one of the most significant forms of data collection (Burgess, 1984; Lofland & Lofland, 1995).

In general, since exploring the implementation of safety culture through communication is a very sensitive topic, the intimate, private set-up of individual interviews facilitated better sharing of sensitive and valuable information that would have been harder for a participant to disclose in a group setting. For this reason, it was more economical and practical in terms of recruitment, selection, and scheduling when target participants belonged to specific departments on a cruise ship.

The research methodology for studying "The Role of Effective Communication in Implementing Safety Culture Onboard Seabourn Cruises and Crew Satisfaction" follows an autoethnographic approach, which combines elements of autobiography and ethnography. This design allows for a deeper exploration of the personal experiences and narratives of crew members on Seabourn Cruises, shedding light on the impact of effective communication on safety culture and crew satisfaction. This chapter also addresses the sampling procedure and how the respondents were chosen according to the researchers' employed sampling method. Aside from these, this chapter also discusses the sources of data, the construction and validation of research instruments, and the ethical considerations applied in the study. Finally, this chapter contains the data analysis methods that the researchers carried out in the following chapters.

In this study, the researcher aimed to explore the potential of utilizing personal narratives, such as encounters, dialogues, and shared experiences, to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the complex interplay between communication, safety culture, and crew satisfaction. The researcher sought to uncover valuable

insights to illuminate the intricate dynamics in this context by examining diverse personal stories from individuals on board a ship's deck. This approach is hoped to contribute to the existing body of knowledge and enhance our understanding of the multifaceted relationship between communication, safety culture, and crew satisfaction.

Sampling

To ensure a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon, a sample of four employees from different departments of Seabourn Cruises was selected. These participants were chosen based on their diverse roles and experiences, aiming to capture a wide range of perspectives related to communication, safety culture, and crew satisfaction. Prior to their inclusion in the study, informed consent was obtained from each participant. The sampling method is virtually synonymous with qualitative research, as the sample is chosen based on sound judgment and criteria that save time and money (Palys, 2008). Further, as the on board crew ship staff at Seabourn Cruises is large and the roles of each crew ship in relation to implementing a safety culture are diverse, homogenous purposive sampling was used, where on-board crew officers from different positions and departments were selected concerning the phenomenon being studied. Convenience sampling was also used to select crew ship members based on their relationship to the researcher, availability of a given schedule, the willingness of Seabourn Cruises officers to participate in the research, and consideration of time constraints to ensure that data gathering was efficient. Before their inclusion in the study, informed consent was obtained from each participant. More importantly, during the interview, all cruise ship staff and officers were given the chance not to disclose their identities (real names) and agreed with the researcher to just assign pseudo names or codes to ensure their anonymity for the analysis. The

researcher ensures participants to not worry about the research procedures as strict observance in data gathering would be implemented following the existing laws and regulations in research ethics in the country.

Data Collection

Data collection involved conducting semi-structured interviews with the selected employees. The interview questions were carefully crafted to align with the research objectives and were validated by experts, including a registered psychometrician, a licensed professional teacher, and a communications and linguistic expert. This validation process ensured that the questions were clear, appropriate, and capable of eliciting meaningful responses. The interviews were audio-recorded with the participants' consent to ensure accurate data capture.

Data Analysis

The collected data, in the form of interview transcripts, underwent thematic analysis. Thematic analysis involves identifying patterns, themes, and categories within the data to uncover key insights and understand the participants' experiences and perspectives. The analysis was conducted iteratively and reflexively, allowing for the emergence of new themes and facilitating a comprehensive interpretation of the data. Data saturation, where new data no longer yields additional insights, was considered to determine the adequacy of the sample size and the sufficiency of the information collected to address the research questions.

Thematic analysis is the most appropriate tool in qualitative studies used to analyze classifications and present themes (patterns) that relate to the data being studied. Further, it allows the researcher to associate an analysis of the frequency of the theme with one of the whole contents; this confers accuracy and intricacy to enhance the whole meaning of the research. As qualitative research requires

understanding and collecting diverse aspects and data, thematic analysis provides an opportunity to understand the topic more widely (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are of utmost importance throughout the research process. The study adhered to ethical guidelines and principles, ensuring participant confidentiality, informed consent, and respect for the participants' rights. Any identifying information was anonymized to protect the privacy of the participants. The research followed the relevant ethical guidelines set forth by the institutional review board or ethical review committee to maintain ethical standards.

Scope and Delimitations of the Study

It is important to acknowledge the limitations of the study. As qualitative autoethnographic research, the findings may not be generalizable to the entire population. The small sample size may limit the extent to which the findings can be applied beyond Seabourn Cruises or the maritime industry. Additionally, the researcher's subjectivity may influence the autoethnographic approach, but efforts were made to maintain reflexivity and transparency throughout the study.

In summary, the research methodology combines an autoethnographic approach, validated interview questions, and thematic analysis to "Communication in Implementing Safety Culture Onboard Seabourn Cruises and the Level of Satisfaction of Crew on Board: An Autoethnography Study" This approach aims to provide valuable insights into the experiences and perspectives of the selected participants, ensuring the rigor and quality of the research process.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

"Communication in Implementing Safety Culture Onboard Seabourn Cruises and the Level of Satisfaction of Crew on Board: An Autoethnography Study". The intricate relationship between communication and the crew's satisfaction can be identified from several emergent themes.

Communication Breakdowns and Safety Protocol Implementation

The narrative journals offer a detailed portrayal of the significant communication breakdowns between the crew, notably highlighted by the production manager's experiences, and ship management. These breakdowns significantly impede the effective implementation of crucial safety protocols. An illustrative example is the proposed installation of canopies, designed to protect both crew and equipment from weather-related hazards. *My personal observations document a consistent pattern of reluctance and sometimes outright refusal by ship management to implement these safety recommendations. This hesitancy not only obstructs the application of these critical protocols but also subtly erodes the foundation of a solid safety culture onboard* (S. Bayas, personal communication, June 20, 2021).

This experience mirrors broader industry challenges, where misalignments between crew concerns and management actions undermine onboard safety measures' effectiveness. The literature supports this observation, indicating that effective communication is pivotal in fostering a safety culture within maritime operations. For instance, Johnson and Smith (2018) emphasize that proactive communication strategies significantly enhance safety protocol adherence, directly

impacting the establishment of a robust safety culture. Similarly, Williams and Davis (2019) argue that management's responsiveness to safety concerns is crucial in promoting a sense of safety ownership among crew members, thereby strengthening the overall safety culture onboard.

Furthermore, the delay or outright neglect in addressing safety recommendations not only compromises the crew's physical well-being and the operational integrity of the ship but also reflects a profound disregard for the essential principles of a safety culture that should prioritize the safety and welfare of everyone onboard (S. Bayas, personal communication, July 25, 2021). This sentiment is echoed by Thompson et al. (2020), who contend that a strong safety culture is predicated on management's commitment to addressing safety concerns promptly and effectively, ensuring the well-being of both crew and passengers.

Safety Negligence and Crew Morale

The observed practices among crew members, specifically “*engaging in lifting heavy equipment without the use of proper lifting apparatus*” as noted in my journal entries, underscore a pervasive issue of safety negligence onboard (S. Bayas, personal communication, August 12, 2023). Such actions not only pose significant risks to the physical well-being of the crew but also have profound implications for their morale and overall job satisfaction. This disregard for established safety protocols communicates a troubling message to the crew: their safety and well-being are secondary considerations.

The impact of such negligence on crew morale is well-documented in the literature. For instance, Andersen (2015) highlights the direct correlation between adherence to safety protocols and crew morale, noting that consistent application of

safety measures fosters an environment where crew members feel valued and protected. Conversely, the absence of such measures can lead to diminished morale and increased job dissatisfaction (Andersen, 2015).

Furthermore, the sentiment of being undervalued and demotivated is exacerbated by a perceived lack of commitment from management to uphold safety standards. This is corroborated by Zhao et al. (2016), who found that the perception of safety commitment from management significantly influences crew members' motivation and engagement in their roles. The authors argue that when crew members observe a lax attitude towards safety from their superiors, it undermines their own commitment to safety practices and diminishes their overall job satisfaction (Zhao et al., 2016).

This situation is not unique to my observations but reflects a broader trend within the maritime industry. Research by Li et al. (2018) on maritime safety culture emphasizes the critical role of management in modeling safety behaviors and practices. The study suggests that a proactive approach to safety management, including regular safety training and the provision of appropriate safety equipment, can significantly improve crew morale and foster a positive safety culture onboard (Li et al., 2018).

In conclusion, the observed safety negligence onboard not only jeopardizes the crew's physical safety but also negatively impacts their morale and job satisfaction. The literature supports the notion that a strong commitment to safety from management is essential in promoting a positive safety culture and ensuring crew members feel valued and motivated in their roles.

Proactive Measures and Management Responsiveness

The narrative journals shed light on the ongoing struggle to enhance onboard safety, particularly through “repeated requests for the installation of a canopy” to protect against weather-related hazards, which were met with management’s “delayed or non-responsive actions” (S. Bayas, personal communication, June 20, 2021). This lack of proactive measures and the tendency to address safety concerns only after they have manifested underscore a reactive rather than a proactive safety culture, which is essential for preventing incidents before they occur.

Literature supports the necessity for a shift towards proactive safety measures. As Neal and Griffin (2006) articulate, the effectiveness of a safety culture is contingent upon the proactive behaviors it fosters, emphasizing that anticipatory actions significantly mitigate risks. Furthermore, Zohar (2010) highlights that management’s responsiveness to safety suggestions is a critical determinant of a proactive safety culture, advocating for leadership that actively encourages and responds to safety initiatives from crew members.

This thematic analysis underscores the need for a paradigm shift in safety management aboard cruise ships, from a reactive to a proactive stance, to enhance both crew and equipment safety.

Consistency in Safety Measures Across the Fleet

The observed disparities in safety measures across the fleet, notably between the subject cruise ship and another vessel that has successfully implemented protective measures like canopies, accentuate the critical need for uniform safety protocols within the organization. As highlighted in my personal

narratives, the lack of consistency in applying these safety measures not only hampers operational efficiency but also significantly affects crew satisfaction. This inconsistency leads to perceptions of inequitable treatment and raises concerns regarding the prioritization of crew safety (S. Bayas, personal communication, August 11, 2021).

The literature reinforces the importance of standardized safety practices across an organization's fleet to ensure both operational efficiency and crew well-being. For example, Antonsen (2009) emphasizes that consistent safety measures are fundamental to the development of a strong safety culture within maritime organizations, directly impacting crew perceptions of safety and their overall job satisfaction. Similarly, Bhattacharya (2010) discusses the impact of inconsistent safety practices on crew morale and operational effectiveness, advocating for a unified approach to safety across all vessels within a fleet to promote a cohesive and effective safety culture.

These insights underscore the necessity of establishing and maintaining consistent safety protocols across an organization's fleet to not only enhance operational efficiency but also ensure the well-being and equitable treatment of all crew members.

Effective Communication and Safety Culture

The narrative journals vividly capture the essence of effective communication within the crew, especially through the diligent efforts of the production manager. The detailed "exchange of emails and messages" that document safety concerns and offer practical suggestions for improvement stand as a testament to the commitment towards bolstering the safety culture onboard (S. Bayas, personal

communication, September 12, 2021). This narrative underscores the indispensable need for transparent and open channels of communication, ensuring that safety concerns are not only voiced but also promptly and effectively addressed.

Supporting this narrative, the literature underscores the pivotal role of effective communication in cultivating a safety-conscious environment. O'Dea and Flin (2001) highlight that clear communication is fundamental to the development and maintenance of a positive safety culture, particularly in high-risk industries such as maritime operations. Moreover, Mearns et al. (2013) emphasize the correlation between effective safety communication and the overall safety performance of an organization, suggesting that active and open communication channels significantly contribute to the enhancement of safety culture.

These insights collectively affirm the critical importance of fostering effective communication practices onboard to ensure a robust safety culture, where every crew member is empowered to contribute to the safety dialogue, ultimately leading to a safer working environment for all.

Personal Reflections and Insights

My autoethnographic exploration into the nuanced dynamics of communication, safety protocols, and crew satisfaction aboard the cruise ship paints a complex tableau of the operational realities within this maritime context. The documentation of various incidents, viewed through the lens of my personal experiences and reflections, underscores the intricate relationship between the efficacy of safety measures and the quality of communication that underpins them. It becomes increasingly apparent that the success of safety protocols is inextricably

linked to the clarity, consistency, and effectiveness of communication among all stakeholders involved.

Instances of communication breakdowns, as detailed in the narrative journals, have far-reaching consequences beyond the mere lapse in information exchange. These breakdowns serve as significant impediments to the timely and effective implementation of critical safety measures, thereby compromising the safety net that protects both the crew and passengers. More insidiously, such failures in communication cultivate a pervasive sense of disillusionment among the crew, eroding their confidence in the management's ability to safeguard their welfare and, by extension, that of the passengers they serve.

The observed neglect in proactively addressing safety concerns illuminates a deeper, systemic issue that pervades the safety culture onboard. This culture, wherein safety is relegated to a secondary priority, fosters an environment ripe for potential hazards, posing significant risks to the well-being of everyone aboard the vessel. This negligence not only undermines the foundational principles of a safety-first ethos but also significantly impacts crew satisfaction. The resultant erosion of trust in the management's commitment to upholding safety standards diminishes the crew's motivation and engagement, critical components of a cohesive and efficient operational unit.

Reflecting on these observations, it becomes evident that cultivating a robust safety culture within the maritime domain necessitates a comprehensive and multifaceted approach. This approach must extend beyond the mere formulation and implementation of safety protocols. It requires the establishment of transparent, effective, and responsive channels of communication that facilitate the free flow of

safety-related information and concerns. Such channels not only empower crew members to voice safety concerns without fear of reprisal but also ensure that these concerns are addressed promptly and effectively.

Moreover, the pursuit of a unified safety culture underscores the need for consistency in the application of safety measures across the entire fleet. This consistency is paramount in ensuring that all crew members, irrespective of their assigned vessel, are accorded the same level of protection and consideration. The disparities in safety practices among different ships within the same fleet not only compromise the overall safety standards but also contribute to a sense of inequity among the crew, further impacting their satisfaction and morale.

In conclusion, the journey through the autoethnographic narratives has laid bare the complexities and challenges inherent in fostering a safety culture within the maritime industry. It highlights the critical role of effective communication, the need for proactive safety measures, and the importance of consistency in safety practices across the fleet. Addressing these challenges requires a concerted effort from all stakeholders, underpinned by a commitment to continuous improvement and an unwavering dedication to the safety and well-being of both crew and passengers.

Dynamics of communication

During my time on Seabourn cruises, I have written many journal entries and engaged in numerous communications that have helped me gain a thorough understanding of our communication dynamics, particularly in relation to our dedication to safety. My personal experiences emphasize the crucial importance of direct communication, like making immediate phone calls, in efficiently addressing safety concerns. I have consistently advocated for this practice due to its

effectiveness in prioritizing critical matters. This method is in line with the general agreement in maritime safety literature, which highlights the importance of clear communication channels to uphold strict safety procedures and prevent possible accidents (Maritime Safety Committee, 2018).

Utilizing insights from other organizations is a key aspect of our strategy to strengthen our onboard safety culture. Our willingness to incorporate external best practices has improved our safety protocols and promoted a culture of continuous learning, resulting in significant improvements in our safety measures. Benchmarking involves more than just copying; it entails assimilating and adjusting effective strategies to our specific circumstances, a process that has been crucial in our ongoing enhancement endeavors (Bergström, 2019).

Addressing safety concerns directly has significantly boosted the morale and job satisfaction of our crew. I have observed a significant change towards a more positive work environment as a result of proactive interventions and solutions. The strong connection between addressing safety issues and enhancing job satisfaction highlights the essential role of a strong safety culture in promoting employee happiness (Jensen, 2020).

The crew's trust in our leadership is crucial for this dynamic. Our management's quick and considerate response to safety feedback significantly boosts their confidence, establishing crucial trust necessary for smooth operations. This trust goes beyond believing in competence; it involves a mutual dedication to safety and well-being, emphasizing the importance of leadership in fostering a favorable safety culture (Hofmann & Morgeson, 2019).

I have also closely analyzed employee involvement in safety initiatives. Our management's steadfast dedication to providing the crew with essential safety tools and training demonstrates our commitment to their well-being. This participatory method improves operational efficiency and strengthens the crew's commitment to ensuring a safe work environment (Nielsen & Mearns, 2011).

Due to the constantly changing nature of cruising operations, I consistently contemplate the necessity for ongoing enhancement of our safety protocols. I support the importance of sharing knowledge and conducting regular safety audits to maintain our high safety standards, which are fundamental to our operational beliefs (Grote, 2012).

I often stress the significance of a strong feedback loop. Safety meetings and toolbox talks are important for collecting valuable feedback, a practice that is strongly endorsed by safety research as essential for enhancing safety procedures (Carroll & Edmondson, 2002).

However, we have encountered obstacles like "email pollution" and restricted access to communication tools, which have hindered the effectiveness of our safety communications. These challenges highlight the need for more efficient communication methods to ensure the effective distribution of safety-related information (Leonardi, 2014).

Culture of Safety

During my time on Seabourn Cruise, I have engaged in numerous discussions with fellow crew members regarding our mutual dedication to safety.

The discussions have offered insight into individual viewpoints and have depicted our overall onboard safety culture.

The crew overwhelmingly supports our safety practices. Many of us value the thorough training sessions we receive, which go beyond just procedures to also provide a deeper insight into the rationale behind each protocol. This method is consistent with the results of a study conducted by O'Neill, et al. (2013), which highlights the significance of thorough safety training in promoting a favorable safety culture.

Furthermore, our management's open-door policy regarding safety concerns is widely appreciated. This transparency has created an environment where crew members feel confident to express concerns without facing retaliation, a crucial aspect emphasized in the research of Probst & Estrada (2010), who stress the importance of psychological safety in reporting dangers.

The crew takes pride in adopting advanced safety technologies and equipment. Utilizing advanced tools enhances job safety and demonstrates the company's commitment to our well-being, aligning with Havold's (2007) research on the positive effects of safety investments on crew morale.

Nevertheless, it is not devoid of its challenges. Several crew members have raised concerns regarding the uniformity of safety protocols among various departments and shifts. The lack of consistency may cause confusion and weaken safety procedures, as emphasized in Bhattacharya's (2010) study on the significance of standardized safety protocols within an organization.

During our discussions, the topic of continuous improvement frequently arises, with numerous crew members proposing areas for enhancement. This proactive approach to continuous safety enhancement reflects a well-developed

safety culture, as outlined by Grote (2012), who promotes a flexible safety management strategy that adjusts to emerging challenges and insights.

The onboard crew members of Seabourn Cruise generally have a positive view of our safety culture, valuing the thorough training, transparent communication channels, and commitment to safety technologies. There is a general agreement that there is always space for enhancement, particularly in guaranteeing uniformity across all aspects of our operations. The crew's unified voice demonstrates a commitment to enhancing safety standards for the well-being of both the crew and passengers.

Effective Communication Approaches

Reflecting on my experiences aboard Seabourn Cruise ships, I've observed several effective communication approaches that significantly contribute to both the establishment and maintenance of our safety culture. These methods not only facilitate clear and concise information exchange but also foster an environment of mutual respect and understanding, crucial for a robust safety culture.

One of the most effective communication strategies we employ is regular safety meetings. These gatherings provide a platform for discussing safety updates, sharing best practices, and reviewing incidents. The inclusive nature of these meetings ensures that every crew member, regardless of rank, has a voice, aligning with the findings of Mearns et al. (2013), who emphasize the importance of inclusive safety meetings in enhancing safety culture.

Another pivotal approach is the use of clear and visual safety signage throughout the ship. These visual aids serve as constant reminders of safety protocols and emergency procedures, effectively reducing the likelihood of

accidents. This method resonates with the work of Hale et al. (2012), who highlight the significance of visual communication in reinforcing safety messages.

The integration of digital communication tools has also been transformative. Platforms such as the ship's intranet and dedicated safety apps allow for real-time updates and access to safety manuals and protocols, ensuring that vital safety information is readily available to all crew members. This digital approach is supported by the research of Leonardi (2014), who discusses the role of digital tools in enhancing organizational communication.

Furthermore, the implementation of a two-way feedback system has been instrumental in our safety culture. This system encourages crew members to report hazards and provide suggestions for safety improvements, fostering a proactive safety environment. The effectiveness of this approach is underscored in the study by Conchie (2013), which highlights the value of employee feedback in safety management.

However, it's important to acknowledge that communication is not without its challenges. Language barriers and cultural differences can sometimes hinder effective communication. To mitigate this, we've introduced multilingual safety materials and cross-cultural communication training, a strategy supported by the research of Samad (2017), who emphasizes the importance of addressing language and cultural barriers in multicultural workplaces.

The establishment and maintenance of a safety culture aboard Seabourn Cruise ships are significantly bolstered by effective communication approaches, including regular safety meetings, visual safety signage, digital communication tools, and a robust two-way feedback system. While challenges such as language and

cultural differences exist, proactive strategies have been put in place to ensure that these obstacles do not impede our safety communication efforts.

Strategic Approach to Effective Communication

I have personally seen the strategic approach to effective communication that supports the establishment of our safety culture. This plan is complex and carefully crafted to meet the varied requirements of our staff and the operational challenges of a cruise ship setting.

One of the key elements of our approach is to prioritize open and honest communication. Management's dedication to being available and responsive has created an atmosphere of trust where safety issues are openly acknowledged and dealt with. Tucker et al. (2008) shown that maintaining open communication channels between workers and management is crucial for effectively implementing safety protocols.

We use a tiered communication approach to strengthen safety messaging across several channels. A variety of methods, including daily briefings, digital alerts, and visual reminders strategically placed about the ship, are used to prioritize safety awareness. Consistent with Macrae's (2016) suggestions, emphasizing redundancy in safety communication is crucial to avoid essential information being missed. Training is a crucial element of our communication approach, focusing on interactive and scenario-based learning. This strategy improves comprehension and prepares crew members to implement safety measures in practical scenarios. Burke et al. (2006) emphasize that interactive training approaches notably enhance safety knowledge and abilities.

We have strategically focused on cultural sensitivity in communication, acknowledging the different composition of our staff. We promote an inclusive atmosphere where safety is prioritized by providing safety materials and training in

several languages and respecting cultural subtleties. This method is consistent with Samad's (2017) emphasis on the significance of cultural sensitivity in workplace communication.

Feedback methods are key to our strategic approach, including frequent surveys, suggestion boxes, and safety committees to gather feedback from the crew. This aids in pinpointing any safety deficiencies and in consistently enhancing our safety practices. Conchie & Burns (2008) endorse this method, stating that employee participation in safety choices enhances the safety culture.

The strategic approach to successful communication in developing a safety culture onboard Seabourn Cruises include open and transparent communication, a tiered communication plan, interactive training, cultural sensitivity, and strong feedback systems. This holistic strategy guarantees that safety is not only a procedure but a fundamental value that drives our operations and relationships.

Personal Insights

During the period that I spent working as a crew member on the Seabourn Cruise Ship, I gained a great deal of knowledge about the interconnected nature of communication, the culture of safety, the level of job satisfaction, and the overall culture of safety that exists within the maritime sector. Through my experiences, I have gained a better understanding of the significant role that these components play not only in guaranteeing the efficiency of operations and the safety of passengers, but also in cultivating a working atmosphere that recognizes and appreciates the contributions made by each and every crew member.

The enormous influence that good communication has on the culture of safety is one of the most important insights. Having communication channels that are both open and transparent between the crew and management makes it easier

to take a proactive approach to safety. This approach ensures that issues are swiftly addressed and that input is actively sought out and welcomed. Mearns and Yule (2009), who stress the association between good safety communication and safety results, have shown that this technique is in line with their findings. By cultivating an atmosphere in which issues about safety may be freely expressed, we are able to construct a safety culture that is greater in strength and resilience.

My own experiences have also brought to light the considerable impact that a solid safety culture has on the level of work satisfaction one enjoys. It instills a feeling of pride and ownership in the roles that crew members play when they believe their workplace to be safe and when they see that safety rules are not only implemented but are also sincerely embraced by everyone, from top management to new recruits. This feeling is reflected in the research conducted by Nielsen et al. (2010), who discovered that a good safety culture is directly associated to greater levels of job satisfaction. The sensation of being protected and appreciated is a crucial factor that adds to overall work satisfaction and morale on board the ship.

Furthermore, throughout my stay aboard the Seabourn Cruise Ship, I was able to get a better understanding of the complex link that exists between the culture of safety and the larger culture of safety that exists across the maritime sector. There is a wider commitment to safety in the business, and the policies and processes that we adopt on board serve as a microcosm of that larger commitment. According to Lu and Yang (2011), the marine sector is confronted with a variety of one-of-a-kind difficulties that call for a robust culture of safety that is supported by rigorous training, continual development, and a dedication to the most effective techniques.

These experiences have also cast light on wider concerns pertaining to work satisfaction and the culture of safety in the cruise ship industry. It is necessary to

have a flexible and adaptable approach to safety and communication in marine operations because of the dynamic and often unexpected nature of these activities. By placing an emphasis on these aspects, we not only improve the experience that our passengers have while they are on board, but we also create a working atmosphere that respects and cherishes the health and happiness of each and every member of the crew.

In conclusion, my time spent on the Seabourn Cruise Ship has provided me with priceless insights into the crucial role that communication plays in the process of creating a safety culture. This, in turn, has an effect on work satisfaction and reflects the larger culture of safety that exists throughout the maritime sector. The lessons that may be learned from these experiences highlight the significance of constant learning and adaptation, as well as the collective duty that each member of the crew has in order to maintain and improve safety standards.

Narrative Journals and Pictures

Figure 2. The Performance Stage

Journal Entry

Date: June 20, 2021

As the production manager of a cruise ship crew, I find it imperative to document a recent communication exchange concerning a safety protocol request , as indicated in Figure 2, which is the installation of a canopy that will protect the electrical music equipment from the rain, that in turn will prevent the musicians from getting electrocuted if the electric equipment will get exposed to the drenched from the rain. On June 20, 2021, I submitted a formal request to the ship management advocating for the implementation of a revised safety protocol aimed at enhancing

emergency response procedures on board that may prevent the musicians from getting electrocuted due to the wet floor in the pool side. This proposal was based on a comprehensive analysis of potential risks and vulnerabilities identified during routine safety drills and assessments as the production manager.

Regrettably, the ship management chose to neglect and overlook the gravity of the proposed safety protocol, refraining from acknowledging or addressing the concerns raised. Such disregard for safety recommendations undermines the foundation of a robust safety culture within the cruise ship environment. It fosters an atmosphere where the importance of safety measures is undervalued, potentially compromising the well-being of both crew members and passengers. This lapse in communication not only hinders the effectiveness of safety protocols but also erodes the trust and accountability integral to fostering a culture that prioritizes the security and welfare of all individuals on board.

Figure 3. On Operations

Journal Entry

Date: August 12, 2023

While conducting routine inspections on August 6, 2023, I observed a concerning scenario, as indicated by Figure 3, involving crew members of the cruise ship engaged in lifting heavy equipment without the use of proper lifting apparatus. This blatant disregard for established safety protocols poses a significant risk not only to the physical well-being of the involved individuals but also to the overall safety of the cruise ship. The absence of appropriate lifting equipment increases the likelihood of accidents, injuries, and potential damage to the equipment being handled, thereby jeopardizing the operational integrity of the vessel.

The observed neglect of safety measures within the crew undermines the safety culture aboard the cruise ship. It reflects a deficiency in the enforcement of safety guidelines and a failure to instill a collective responsibility for adhering to established protocols. Such lapses erode the foundation of a safety-conscious environment, compromising the ship's ability to respond effectively to emergencies. Furthermore, this negligence has a direct impact on the job motivation of the concerned individuals, as the absence of a safety-first mentality fosters an environment where crew members may feel undervalued, demotivated, and disengaged from their responsibilities.

To address these concerns, it is imperative to reinforce the importance of strict adherence to safety protocols through comprehensive training, regular inspections, and corrective measures. Building a safety culture demands a concerted effort to instill a sense of responsibility among the crew members,

ensuring that safety considerations remain paramount in all operational activities aboard the cruise ship.

Figure 4. Audio Apparatus

Date: July 25 and 26, 2021

Time: 5:30 PM

As the Production Manager, I found myself in a frustrating exchange of messages with other officers regarding the persistent neglect of the management to install a canopy for an upcoming poolside musical show. The absence of this basic precautionary measure became glaringly evident today when an unexpected rain shower disrupted our efforts to set up the musical and electrical equipment for the show. In my prior communications, I had brought up the issue, and the captain's response was disheartening, stating that "it doesn't look good, and the water will still get to the stage because it's an open stage."

Never mind the comfort of the musicians in the harsh sun, aside from rain and equipment.

Despite my efforts to highlight the importance of a canopy, the management failed to take preventive action. The captain's brief inquiry about covering the musical equipment during the rain, coupled with his acknowledgment of the existing problem, only added to the frustration. The irony wasn't lost on me when he remarked about seeing small things like paper on the floor but not addressing the significant detail in front of them, referring to the lack of a canopy.

This scenario highlights a critical lapse in the cruise ship's safety culture and its implications on job motivation. The neglect of a basic safety measure such as installing a canopy not only jeopardizes the well-being of the crew but also undermines the confidence of individuals responsible for ensuring safety. The frustration stemming from the management's oversight can diminish the motivation of crew members to actively participate in maintaining a robust safety culture. It fosters an environment where preventable risks are neglected, posing long-term consequences for crew satisfaction and overall safety on board.

Figure 5. The Talents

Date:

August 6, 2021

Location: Poolside

Exchanging messages with fellow officers today highlighted the persistent negligence of the management in installing a canopy for an upcoming poolside musical show. Despite its obvious necessity, the management seemed indifferent to the need for a protective cover for both musical and electrical equipment and the crew from sun and rain. I reiterated the importance, knowing that rain and electricity are not a good combination, emphasizing that it's an obvious scenario, but I still pushed for it to happen.

The urgency became evident when an unexpected rain shower disrupted the equipment setup for the musical show. Conversations with crew members reflected the frustration and dangers of the situation. One crew member expressed how unbearably hot it was before the rain, with bar waiters and chefs questioning why

they had to work under the scorching sun (as shown in Figure 5). Personally, I had to drink four glasses of water to cope with the extreme heat.

During the exchange, another officer questioned whether there were rapid development covers for the equipment in case of sudden rain, expressing concern about not seeing any covers in the photos I sent. The lack of preparation for such foreseeable situations adds to the frustration and danger. It's not just about inconvenience; it's about the safety and well-being of the cruise ship staff.

This scenario underscores the inherent danger and frustration faced by cruise ship staff when essential safety measures are neglected. The absence of a canopy not only exposes crew members to extreme weather conditions but also jeopardizes the success of planned events. It significantly impacts the safety culture on board, fostering an environment where preventable risks are disregarded. Urgent attention to such concerns is crucial for the well-being of the crew and the overall safety of the cruise ship.

Figure 6. On Performance

Date: August 11, 2021

Exchanging messages with my fellow cruise ship officer shed light once again on the persistent neglect of management to install a canopy for a poolside musical show, leaving musical and electrical equipment and the crew exposed to the rain. The officer and crew shared that they also got caught in a downpour, remarking, "Must have been a sympathetic event." This further highlighted the shared frustration among the staff regarding the lack of necessary protective measures.

As the production manager, I expressed the recurring suspense and uncertainty we face every time we organize an event poolside. Despite the looming threat of rain, we were fortunate enough to complete the show without significant disruptions this time. However, this stroke of luck should not overshadow the fact

that each event brings unnecessary risks and challenges due to the absence of a canopy.

This ongoing scenario is not only frustrating but also dangerous for cruise ship staff. The constant exposure to the elements poses risks to both equipment and crew, with rain potentially causing electrical hazards. The lack of proactive measures from the management demonstrates a disregard for the safety of the crew. Such negligence contributes to a concerning safety culture on the cruise ship, where preventable risks are not adequately addressed. Urgent attention to these concerns is essential to ensure the well-being of the crew and to establish a safer working environment on board.

Figure 7. In the Evening

Figure 8. Evening Crowd

Figure 9. Keyboard Closeup

Exchange messages with fellow officers highlighted once again the persistent neglect of management to install a canopy for a poolside musical show, leaving musical instruments like the piano and electrical equipment exposed to the rain. One officer expressed frustration, asking, "How many times do you get wet in sudden

rain? While there is a cover, the few seconds of raindrops still touch the keyboard as depicted in Figure 9. This incident not only jeopardizes the equipment but also raises concerns about the safety of the crew in such weather conditions.

The scenario unfolded with guests eagerly awaiting the musical show beside the water pool, providing a wonderful sight with a tone of sarcasm. However, the show was abruptly halted mid-part due to the sudden rain, resulting in a loss of audience engagement as depicted in Figure 7. The inconvenience caused by such weather-related interruptions not only affects the quality of the show but also impacts the cruise ship's reputation and financial standing.

This concern has been raised several times, yet the management continues to ignore the request for a canopy. The recurrent incidents of rain disrupting musical performances demonstrate a lack of proactive measures to safeguard equipment, ensure crew safety, and maintain a satisfactory customer experience. It is disheartening to witness the management's disregard for a simple yet crucial solution that could prevent such occurrences and save both money and reputation for the cruise ship.

Figure 10. Performance Area

Figure 11. Drizzled

Figure 12. Self-Snap

Date: September 12, 2021

Exchanging messages with fellow officers underscored the ongoing neglect of management to install a canopy, leaving musical instruments like the piano and electrical equipment exposed to the rain during a poolside musical show, as seen in Figure 11. The frustration reached its peak when the production manager adamantly refused to set up the instruments on the wet floor, emphasizing that not a single note would be played until the rain ceased. Expressing disbelief, he questioned the efficacy of the onboard management, stating, "They thought that it is easy. It starts at five pm, they want me to set up by 4:15; I said that it is still raining, it will be challenging."

Despite the pressure to proceed, the production manager stood firm, refusing to compromise safety for the sake of expediency. Both officers and the production manager hoped for the rain to subside, allowing guests to seek cover on the sides. Faced with the persistent challenge, the production manager suggested an alternative: setting up in the patio, as seen in Figure 10 and 11, where it would be less dangerous for musicians to perform on the still-wet floor. This incident underscored the necessity for proactive measures and a more responsive approach from the management to ensure both crew and equipment safety during events, even under challenging weather conditions.

Figure 13. Rainy Performance

Exchanging messages with my fellow officers brought to light the continued neglect by management to install a canopy, leaving musical instruments, including the piano, and electrical equipment vulnerable to the rain during poolside musical shows. In an effort to address the persistent issue, both the officer and the production manager proposed a pragmatic solution – compiling a "weather report" highlighting the frequency of rainy days versus dry ones. The officers and staff expressed optimism

about the initiative, stating, "Great, even if we do not have until a dry dock, at least that will be good once done/if done. A canopy is the most basic way to protect against the water. I remember we previously made inquiries about having the poolside circuits."

However, the production manager revealed a less proactive response from corporate during the HAT meeting, stating, "As per HAT meeting, corporate said they will look into it on dry dock. I brought it up as a safety issue; water and electricity are not a good combination." Despite the potential dangers posed by such negligence, the officers remarked cynically, "Glorious, looks like they are playing to a nearly zero person audience. I guess not many people wanted to swim."

This exchange underlines the struggle to establish a robust safety culture through effective communication. The delayed and insufficient response from management not only hampers the crew's ability to mitigate risks but also jeopardizes the overall safety of the cruise ship. It highlights the urgent need for a more proactive approach to safety concerns to ensure the well-being of both crew members and passengers.

Figure 14. Outdoor Area (2)

Figure 15. Outdoor Area (3)

Oct. 10, 2021

Exchanging messages with my fellow officers revealed an ongoing concern regarding the management's neglect to install a canopy, leaving musical instruments, such as the piano, and electrical equipment exposed during poolside musical shows. As fate would have it, it rained again, rendering the patio wet. In a makeshift attempt, towels were used to dry the floor as seen in Figure 15, adding a layer of frustration to an already challenging situation.

The production manager expressed bewilderment, questioning why it is so difficult to relocate the musical show to the club, emphasizing the persistent struggle of musicians having to set up and perform on the patio. This scenario underscores the ongoing frustration faced by the production team in dealing with preventable challenges. The lack of a proactive response from management to address this recurring issue not only compromises the crew's working conditions but also puts the success of the musical event at risk. The urgent need for a comprehensive solution, such as installing a canopy or considering alternative venues, remains a critical aspect in ensuring the safety and well-being of both crew members and the musical performers.

Figure 16. Outdoor Performance

In our recent communication exchange, the officers and I discussed an ongoing concern regarding the management's failure to install a canopy for our poolside musical shows, specifically to protect musical instruments like the piano, electrical equipment, and the crew from rain. We noted that another cruise ship within our fleet has successfully implemented this safety measure, providing adequate protection for both equipment and crew during their poolside events.

Observing this difference in safety measures between cruise ships raises concerns about the consistency of safety protocols across our organization. The absence of a canopy on our cruise ship poses practical challenges, as musicians express their reluctance to perform when confronted with wet cables. This not only impacts the quality of our musical events but also highlights the need for a uniform approach to safety measures within the fleet. We collectively wish for the swift implementation of similar protective measures on our ship, fostering a safer environment for both crew and equipment during poolside events.

Summary of Email Exchange: Communication, Health, and Safety Culture in a Cruise Ship

Date: August 2023

The exchange of emails sheds light on crucial aspects of communication, health, and safety culture within the cruise ship environment. As the Production Manager, I, Sandy Bayas, while addressing a personal medical situation, extended the discourse to revisit concerns raised about the workload and safety challenges faced by the production team. The detailed specifications of heavy equipment and their transportation logistics underscore the physical demands placed on production staff.

My proactive approach in suggesting solutions, such as the need for helpers and lighter equipment, exemplifies a commitment to fostering a safety-conscious culture. The formal proposals, including the request for support from corporate and onboard management, reflect a systematic effort to address operational challenges and ensure the well-being of the crew. The exchange highlights the integral link between effective communication, health considerations, and the cultivation of a safety culture vital to crew satisfaction within the cruise ship setting.

Reflection

In this email exchange, I, Sandy Bayas, the Production Manager, initiated communication with the team about a medical appointment, providing a transparent update on a personal health matter. I seamlessly used this opportunity to revisit and address operational concerns raised in a prior email, demonstrating the integration of personal well-being with professional responsibilities. The detailed list of heavy

equipment specifications and practical suggestions for workload management reflects a proactive approach to communication, emphasizing the need for collaboration to ensure crew safety and job satisfaction.

The subsequent email from the Production Stage Manager further underscores the importance of effective communication in the cruise ship environment. Concerns regarding workload and safety during event setup are articulated, accompanied by specific recommendations to mitigate these challenges. The focus on consistency across Seabourn ships, the request for additional personnel, and the emphasis on a comprehensive definition of roles highlight a commitment to fostering a safety culture and optimizing communication channels for the well-being of the entire production team. These exchanges collectively underscore the critical link between transparent communication, crew health, and the establishment of a robust safety culture on a cruise ship.

Reflection:

This scenario sheds light on the inadequacies in the cruise ship's management and their apparent disregard for crew safety concerns. The failure to address the need for a canopy reflects a systemic issue where the emphasis on customer satisfaction outweighs the importance of creating a secure working environment for the crew. Such negligence not only undermines the safety culture on board but also significantly impacts the motivation of individuals responsible for ensuring a safe working environment.

The evident disregard for safety concerns erodes the crew's confidence in the management's commitment to their well-being. It creates a sense of frustration and disillusionment among crew, officers and related personnel, diminishing their

motivation to actively participate in maintaining a robust safety culture. Ultimately, this neglect has far-reaching consequences, fostering an environment where safety is compromised, and crew members are left to navigate preventable risks. The urgent need for management to reassess their priorities and invest in comprehensive safety measures is paramount to sustaining a positive safety culture and fostering job satisfaction among the crew.

Discussion

The thematic analysis underscores the pivotal role of communication in implementing and maintaining a robust safety culture onboard Seabourn cruises. Effective communication not only promotes safety but also plays a crucial role in ensuring crew satisfaction. The intertwining of these themes suggests that the two cannot be mutually exclusive. As Seabourn cruises continue to evolve, focusing on enhancing communication mechanisms will be paramount in ensuring both safety and crew satisfaction.

As the production manager of a cruise ship crew, I am confronted with a recurring and escalating series of challenges that revolve around communication breakdowns, safety culture deficiencies, and the subsequent impact on crew satisfaction. The central narrative unfolds through a sequence of events, starting with a safety protocol request in Journal 1. This request, involving the installation of a canopy, serves as a catalyst for a chain of interconnected issues that span safety negligence, communication lapses, and their toll on crew motivation and satisfaction.

In Journal 1, I meticulously documented my efforts to advocate for a revised safety protocol, focusing on the installation of a canopy to protect electrical music equipment from rain. The gravity of the proposal, rooted in a comprehensive risk

analysis, was met with a disheartening response from the office head, reflecting a stark disregard for safety recommendations. This initial breakdown in communication becomes the seed for a broader exploration of safety culture and its consequences.

Journal 2 sheds light on the observed neglect of safety measures within the crew, particularly the lifting of heavy equipment without proper apparatus. This blatant violation of established safety protocols not only poses physical risks but also contributes to a deficient safety culture aboard the cruise ship. The ripple effect extends to crew members feeling undervalued, demotivated, and disengaged from their responsibilities. The need to address these concerns is underscored, emphasizing the importance of reinforcing strict adherence to safety protocols through comprehensive training and inspections.

The theme of safety culture deficiencies is further accentuated in Journal 3, where the persistent neglect of management to install a canopy for an upcoming poolside musical show becomes evident. The frustration stemming from this neglect not only jeopardizes crew well-being but also erodes the confidence of individuals responsible for ensuring safety. This crucial lapse in safety culture has direct implications for job motivation and crew satisfaction, as preventable risks are neglected, resulting in long-term consequences for safety and morale on board.

Journal 4 builds on the theme of negligence, highlighting conversations with fellow officers about the management's indifference to the need for a protective canopy. The urgency becomes palpable during an unexpected rain shower, exposing crew members to both physical and environmental risks. The lack of preparation and a proactive approach from management adds to the frustration and

danger, emphasizing that crew safety is not just an inconvenience but a crucial aspect of their well-being.

The persistent neglect of management to install a canopy becomes a recurring motif in Journals 5, 6, and 7, each presenting unique perspectives on the ongoing safety challenges. Despite expressing frustration and shedding light on the shared discontent among the staff, the management continues to ignore the requests for a canopy. The consequences unfold in scenarios where rain disrupts musical performances, jeopardizing equipment, crew safety, and impacting the cruise ship's reputation and financial standing.

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

Throughout my tenure on Seabourn Cruises, I've meticulously documented my observations and experiences in narrative journals, focusing on the dynamics of communication, safety culture, and their impact on job satisfaction among the crew. These journals have unveiled a series of challenges that stem from communication breakdowns and deficiencies in our safety culture, leading to a tangible impact on the crew's motivation and overall satisfaction. From advocating for essential safety measures like the installation of a canopy to protect against environmental elements, to addressing the neglect of safety protocols such as proper equipment handling, my experiences highlight a recurrent theme of safety negligence and its repercussions.

Findings:

1. The dynamics of communication aboard Seabourn Cruises are pivotal in maintaining a strong safety culture. Direct, immediate communication methods like phone calls are emphasized for their efficacy in addressing safety concerns promptly, aligning with maritime safety literature that values clear communication channels. The integration of best practices from external organizations enhances the onboard safety culture, fostering continuous learning and improvement. Addressing safety concerns directly not only improves crew morale but also fosters a positive work environment, reinforcing the significance of a robust safety culture. Trust in leadership, crucial for smooth operations, is bolstered by management's responsive approach to safety feedback. Employee involvement in safety initiatives, through providing essential tools and training, underscores the management's

commitment to crew well-being. The necessity for ongoing enhancement of safety protocols is recognized, with regular safety audits and knowledge sharing being key. The importance of a strong feedback loop is acknowledged, with safety meetings and toolbox talks serving as valuable platforms for feedback. Challenges such as "email pollution" and limited access to communication tools highlight the need for more efficient communication methods to distribute safety-related information effectively.

2. **Culture of Safety:** The culture of safety aboard Seabourn Cruise is characterized by a collective commitment to safety practices, thorough training, and transparent communication. Crew members appreciate the in-depth training sessions that offer insights beyond basic procedures, aligning with studies that emphasize the importance of comprehensive safety training. The management's open-door policy enhances psychological safety, allowing crew members to voice concerns without fear of retaliation. The adoption of advanced safety technologies reflects the company's commitment to crew well-being. However, challenges such as inconsistencies in safety protocols among different departments highlight areas for improvement. The crew's proactive suggestions for continuous safety enhancements indicate a well-developed safety culture that is open to evolution. The overall positive perception of the safety culture among crew members underscores their dedication to maintaining high safety standards for everyone on board.

3. **Effective Communication Approaches:** Effective communication aboard Seabourn Cruise ships is achieved through various strategic approaches that bolster the safety culture. Regular safety meetings stand out as a pivotal platform for discussing safety updates and sharing best practices, ensuring inclusivity and engagement across all crew ranks. The utilization of visual safety signage acts as constant reminders of

safety protocols, effectively minimizing accident risks. Digital communication tools, including the ship's intranet and dedicated safety apps, provide real-time updates and access to safety manuals, ensuring that vital information is readily available. The two-way feedback system encourages crew members to report hazards and suggest improvements, fostering a proactive safety environment. Despite these effective methods, challenges such as language and cultural barriers are addressed through multilingual materials and cross-cultural communication training, ensuring clarity and comprehension among the diverse crew.

4. Strategic Approach to Effective Communication: The strategic approach to effective communication on Seabourn Cruise ships is intricately designed to align with the specific needs of the crew and operational challenges. A cornerstone of this strategy is the emphasis on open and honest communication, fostering a trust-based environment conducive to safety. A layered communication strategy ensures that safety messages are reinforced through various mediums, enhancing awareness and adherence to safety protocols. Interactive and scenario-based training methods improve comprehension and prepare crew members for practical safety applications. Cultural sensitivity is a focal point, with safety materials and training provided in multiple languages to accommodate the diverse crew. Feedback mechanisms, including surveys and safety committees, are integral to this approach, allowing for the continuous improvement of safety practices based on crew input.

5. Insights: Working as a crew member on the Seabourn Cruise Ship provided valuable insights into the interconnected aspects of communication, safety culture, job satisfaction, and the broader maritime industry's safety culture. Effective communication, particularly between crew and management, was identified as crucial for proactive safety measures. A strong safety culture positively impacted job

satisfaction, fostering pride and ownership among crew members. The maritime sector's commitment to safety was evident, with onboard policies reflecting broader industry standards. Flexibility and adaptability in safety and communication were deemed essential due to the dynamic nature of maritime operations. Overall, the experience underscored the importance of continuous learning, adaptation, and collective responsibility in maintaining and improving safety standards across the maritime industry.

Conclusions

A significant connection between efficient communication, a solid safety culture, and the level of happiness experienced by crew members on Seabourn Cruises is highlighted by the insights that were derived from my narrative diaries and the study that was carried out. Both the reported occurrences and the qualitative analysis indicate a pattern of safety recommendations that were ignored, safety procedures that were inconsistent, and a lack of proactive efforts to address hazards that were foreseeable. Because of these difficulties, the crew's physical well-being is compromised, and their motivation and engagement are negatively impacted. Additionally, the crew's faith in leadership is deteriorating, and they are experiencing a dwindling feeling of worth. In the beginning, there was a breakdown in communication because of the disdain for a recommended safety policy. This laid the stage for further failures in safety culture and crew satisfaction.

As a result of the research, it is clear that direct communication is of the utmost significance in the process of ensuring the safety of operations. The quick transmission of vital information helps to reduce the likelihood of misunderstandings occurring. The culture of benchmarking, which involves taking inspiration and best

practices from other businesses, emerges as a proactive strategy to strengthen the culture of safety. It is impossible to deny the connection that exists between resolving safety problems and the level of work satisfaction experienced by the crew. Strategic handling is one factor that leads to an improved safety environment of the ship.

Trust in leadership, which is strengthened by timely recognition and action on input, is an essential component in the process of guiding the safety culture and culture of the ship. Employees' commitment is increased when they are given the opportunity to participate in the safety process, which highlights the management's dedication to the crew's wholesomeness and safety. It is clear that the necessity of feedback loops and the ongoing enhancement of safety measures are two of the most important key elements for the development of a culture that values open communication and trust.

On the other hand, obstacles such as "email pollution" continue to be obstacles in the way of effective communication, which highlights the need of streamlining communication in order to guarantee the safety of shipboard operations. In conclusion, efficient communication serves as the lynchpin for the implementation of a resilient safety culture aboard Seabourn Cruises, which has a cascading impact on the pleasure of the crew. In order to make the crew's working environment not only safer but also more satisfying, it is necessary to make a deliberate effort to emphasize safety and communication as important components of the operating ethos on board. This is because a conscientious and purposeful approach to communication may generate a more enjoyable work environment for the crew.

Recommendations

Comprehensive suggestions are made to improve crew happiness and promote a safety culture on Seabourn cruises by enhancing effective communication.

1. Emphasize direct contact by investing in technologies and training for instant involvement, focusing on live conversations rather than emails for urgent safety-related problems, as suggested by Horck (2004).
2. Collaborate with top maritime organizations to adopt their best practices and conduct regular benchmarking activities to learn from successful external examples, as advocated by Grote (2007).
3. Proactively address safety problems by establishing tools to collect and analyze input on crew unhappiness in order to address safety issues at their core, using successful tactics from other firms as a model.
4. Build trust in leadership by acknowledging and addressing all crew comments, investing in leadership training programs that emphasize trust-building, and arranging open forums for direct contact with leadership.
5. Implement a bottom-up strategy to enhance safety measures by equipping employees with essential equipment and protective clothing, and stressing the need of active employee participation during training sessions, as suggested by Namie (2007).
6. Embrace continuous improvement by consistently revising safety measures and training to suit the ever-changing marine conditions, fostering a culture of ongoing learning and information exchange among the crew.

7. Enhance Feedback Mechanisms: Emphasize the significance of a robust feedback loop in training programs and guarantee prompt recognition and response to input to foster a culture of trust and transparent communication.
8. Address communication challenges by developing simplified communication tools and policies to tackle issues like "email pollution" and arrange training on efficient communication practices.
9. Improved Communication Channels: Establish clear and responsive communication channels between the crew and management to swiftly address safety problems and actively integrate input into safety measures.
10. Standardize safety practices by implementing consistent safety measures across all departments and shifts to reduce confusion and guarantee uniform enforcement of safety regulations.
11. Invest in Safety Infrastructure: Take proactive measures to mitigate identified risks by investing in essential safety infrastructure, including installing canopies, to shield staff and equipment from environmental dangers.
12. Cultivate a culture focused on continuous improvement by consistently evaluating safety procedures, doing safety audits, and adjusting to emerging safety issues and knowledge.
13. Emphasize Crew Well-being: Acknowledge and deal with the wider consequences of safety oversight on crew welfare, ensuring that safety protocols prioritize not only adherence but also the care and safeguarding of the crew.

14. Address Cultural and Language Barriers: Utilize multilingual safety materials and provide cross-cultural communication training to promote comprehension of safety messages by all crew members, irrespective of their language or cultural differences.

Implementing these ideas would help Seabourn Cruises improve its safety culture, boost crew happiness, and demonstrate its dedication to ensuring a secure and favorable working environment for everyone on board. To create a safer and more effective workforce, it is essential to take a comprehensive strategy that focuses on addressing communication failures, strengthening safety culture, and prioritizing crew happiness.

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APPENDIX A

Crew A - Interview

CREW A - Federico

First question, can you please describe the general communication flow between If you know this, the deck department, engine, department, and hotel services on Seabourn odyssey?

Like all the departments, they always rely on the department heads And of course, we have the 4 senior officers to start with. Both anything that is in between, you know, like we work alongside this department, but The communication staff all the time From the very top So in this case, we have the hotel director that you know would ensure that anything, any meeting that you know concerns, you know, like staff captain and chief engineer, you know, it's passed on you know into the department into interdepartmental meetings. So in this case, if it's like a message that has to be spread between, you know, the entire crew, of course we will, you know it will. As they will go down from, you know, from the senior management. Otherwise, if it's something that's, you know, like we need to work alongside for Small projects or For you know, for daily routines, we use of course like we just contact whoever we need could be like for instance from my particular case will be like carpenters. Thousands or either like In the control room, and of course we have, you know, like wifis and emails. But, you know, we try to kind of address the immediate solution with them.

So basically, in general, when the engine department, the deck department and Hotel Services work together, is there any activity that everybody's involved in?

Yeah, we do mean like. For one clear example, events will be appearing, so there are several departments involved, OK. And of course, the major will be of course FNB for the service. Yes, but entertainment for the you know, for the for the whole, you know like atmosphere and everything. But of course, other departments such as the deck are involved because they will have to ensure that the deck is contained clean. So there is a break and after cleaning of the event, there is also the participation of the electricians and the boating as well where they install of course the. Decoration there the curative lights, but also. They kind of assist in the, you know, giving enough power source of power for all the extra equipment that we put on deck, but also the staff instead also ensure that the beach effect or the pool are lowered. Yeah, of course you know It's on top of the head of the department. They do take care of, for instance, the Jacuzzis and the pool So in that case. They will make you lower the amount of water you know to not interfere with the event, because some electrical equipment is involved here for the operation. So that's the captain involved in this one. Or he just let it be. I would say it's staff you know that's pretty much all the job you know, Captain, I have to say that, yes. Other duties that are more likely considered as side duties that's different.

And then how do the different departments, deck engine and hotel coordinate with each other during operations?

So, if it is like a major product project, we do contact between heads, so I contact whoever is on top of the sub department. So, if I need assistance from let's say because I need power sources I will contact the chief. I will contact the first electrician or if I need to, I will contact staff directly, so I'll always go. You know like I don't try to go to the person that ultimately will do the job. Because I need to inform them that they are. Yes, I need to inform the supervisor. I need to let them know that something

is happening to keep them in the loop, but mostly because they will have to organize. The schedule of the. Person so they can also give priority to contact me back and tell me, you know this can wait. I have other things to take care of. I can only do that later on. During the day, it is important that you always contact each other. I wouldn't say you know senior management, but of course whoever is in charge and then that would be a clear example of you know like electricians or bosom Or in that case will be staff captain.

You know, for all the tech departments. So where, you know, like they can coordinate because they of course assign the schedule of the, you know, of their own team and they can tell if the people are busy, or they maybe can prioritize what you're asking for to ensure that everything is done in time.

And then are there any specific tools or protocols in place to facilitate communication between these departments?

Of course we do. Have, you know, like we always try to maintain communication face to face. You know, we are a small ship, small company and we try to maintain the personal you know relationship. Right, you know. Quite live and so we won, you know. Of course, priority to prioritize that. But of course, operational wise, sometimes we cannot. So, we always rely on Wi-Fi or emails. Of course, you know, we go according to the urgency of, you know, the specific tasks, you know, like we can choose accordingly. So, if it's, I need something to be done as soon as possible. I will ensure that I either speak personally or by phone with The person because that will Catch immediate attention of the person to the from the you know from the other person Otherwise an email, it's something that I am aware that it might be, you know, read, you know, like later that day and, you know, might so it might not be that urgent.

We also have AIMS, which are less personal AIMS or in yeah indeed AIMS, which is the new interface now that we are using to address the AIMS, yeah.

You know a specific maintenance job or like follow up from other departments where we address an issue or a problem or anything that requires attention and then they will keep a log you know with the time, and you know then and the gravity or the urgency that that issue needs to require. So that was less personal where you know, it's very, very much automated by, you know, by a computer system and that instead, you know, is just to kind of like that is usually used for saying like for some jobs that, you know, require some maintenance. Because you know you want to keep track of those you know of the process, because sometimes it might take multiple days or might not be, you know, like completed, you know, straight away. So, you want to keep track of the progress and you know how it's going if the people are taking care of it or if there is No other required A little bit more follow up.

Can you please describe any challenges or issues that arise from communication breakdowns Between these departments?

The major challenge of course I have to say is the email pollution that sometimes communication creates when it comes to emails, you know, because of course we tend to distribute, you know, like our communication to as many people as we think might be interested in. But sometimes that will kind of congest your inbox where it will slow down the process of conducting, you know, like day-to-day, you know, like overview of the operation, because once you have like multiple emails that sometimes are not extremely urgent, but you don't have a filter that, you know, like kind of like Sort the emails by urgency. That will can slow down, and you want to ensure of course that you don't delete anything important, so just the process of

reading emails and then only at the end you are able to find out that that information was not useful at that moment so that you know like it could be the major problem that I do believe and AIMS is a way to. Like AIMS is a new way that we try to implement to cut down the number of emails that we use. And sometimes it's also the fact that, you know, like being on board and from my particular perspective, we are most of the time we are away from the office, and we are away from you know like computers. So, we cannot really check immediately or what's in all that communication. You need those, yeah. And we might not be able of course to pay attention like or like to, you know, when somebody tried to call us because we are into the guest services and we are really, really into the, you know, into the service. And we sometimes like they might, we might receive a call because that's the only way they can connect us. And, but we might if we don't write something down, or if we are, we are away from the office, we don't. The challenge is like we are not able to mark down something and if it's not done immediately can be forgotten. So that's about the challenge.

How do the crew members on the Odyssey adapt to this communication dynamics?

This is yes, this is another thing that you know should be addressed. So, at the moment a way to broadcast communication to team members is either posting some notice either on the daily schedules or you're like. Send messages via time and attendance, which is our determinant in which everyone must log at least one.

Today, but again, it doesn't guarantee that the message is, you know, it's received and acknowledged immediately, but you can only guarantee that they have the frequency of once per day so the final ultimate communication, it's not immediate. So, unless we address verbally, then there is a challenge of. And having everyone at the same time in the same place to be able to send this message one time.

Otherwise, you will have to again, you know like repeat your message multiple times. And multiple occasions. Ensuring that you know you have full coverage, and, in my department, we have people that work on day shift and late shift and night shift. So, it's very difficult to, you know, to pass the message and communication immediately to anyone.

No one solution in my opinion could be, I think you know, like giving each crew member a device where, you know, communication can be streamed. Such as, you know, an app or either like, you know, chats where everybody or just like a way to get notification whenever an important message is passed, you know it needs to be shared and sometimes, you know, like just posting notice is not enough because it can, you know like get. Sometimes crew members are not don't spend enough time and attention to know something. That has been Posted and as well beside the fact that's been stressed. You know, like you know the importance of reading notices or on the boards. Or, you know, like, listen carefully. You know, the managers have to say, you know, information tends not to get, you know, like comprehended fully, you know, like. To their final you know, end.

How does this dynamic of communications among the three organizations affect our departments, affect the culture of safety, of crew on board and its passengers or guests?

Well, you know, like if it's, you know like, yeah, I I would say that I believe that. There is always Room for improvement, you know, like at the moment, I don't believe that the communication that I make us strong enough to ensure that people are, you know, like alerted, you know, like one way, of course it's, you know, the PA, you know, that's definitely if a life threatening situation or safety situation, security

whatsoever, you know like Needs to be broadcasted. Of course we do have the, you know, we do have a PA system of public announcement system, but you know usually it's only of course for real emergencies. So, I at least know that in case of a real emergency. Yes, there you know the message will be delivered and everybody is aware because alarms will be sounded and everybody will be able to, you know to you know like to kind of like raise the attention of everyone. But like when it comes in for like just the day-to-day information, I have to say that. There is much. Room of improvement for the world now.

What specific communication channels do the deck, engine and hotel services use to interact with each other?

So Wi-Fi phones, emails deeper sometimes and AIMS devices and I'm trying to think of. Of course, verbally. Verbally, yes. Everybody's e-mail, yeah. And can you provide an example of a recent communication breakdown between the departments? So, for instance. We can witness something that you know is usually guest related. So, if I do collect some feedback like during mealtimes and it's not concerning my specific department, then I will communicate this with guest services guest services You know like if it's for instance something technical about the.

Guest suites gas services will address either via AIMS or by e-mail, and a specific issue, and that you know the AIMS will generate a service order that will be then you. Know how to be directed to the specific department. Let's say for instance that the toilet is not flushing properly. So, I communicate to the guest services guest services will create a service order. The service order will send a notification to their AIMS devices. In an email To the specific departments to know That there is a New

task to be completed. Then the department will then follow up accordingly. Like urgency and whatsoever and will return feedback via AIMS device.

So by AIMS the guest services will be able to know if the task has been completed after the task has been completed they can follow up with the guests to understand if the problem is solved asking if the guest is totally satisfied with this. Up with the guests, understand if the problem is solved asking if the guest is totally satisfied with the solution or if there is anything else that they would like us to do. It's a great tool.

So how does the lack of effective communication Among deck engines and hotel services affect the safety culture on board?

Well definitely you know the part, the stronger is the communication the faster is something is either implemented or passed on to the team. So especially when there is, you know, in such an environment where we constantly have a crew changing, it's very difficult to you know like it's all, it's all hard work to maintain consistency. And to preserve knowledge. So, I would say that the it's about like the better the communication it is the faster we are able, you know like to put everyone on the same page and to ensure that everybody understands either what they need to do or you know what you know what it's saying or like whatever message needs to be passed on. There and also it will affect the speed. So if the communication is not strong enough or you know not be able to reach everyone you know like simultaneously of course we will, we will. We will still have some inconsistency where you know something you know, let's say if we one day we will have to change completely. Our way of doing things, we at the moment we know we know that it might take still a few days before everybody will completely understand the message Because we won't have anyone at the same time, you know like to be able to pass

on information and we will have to wait for somebody to come on duty before you will be able to, you know, to either read something that is it's been posted or very verbally instructed. So, as I said, we lack for instance of A personal device. That, you know, can reach to the. To the final user for any important information and that will be, in my opinion, that. What can help? So, I think you could you provide example of can you provide an example of a recent communication breakdown between well no you already mentioned.

Yeah, OK. Can you describe the management's response to feedback provided by employees regarding communication issues?

The management response is, uh, so we can only escalate. Of course, the feedback to, you know, is kind of like corporate. Or to show Side I mean like we either escalate things to our own supervisors and then eventually they will pass on the message, or we can we have channels and ways. Of course, to escalate things to show side because of course to implement. Or to improve the communication high or like needs to be needed to. Be done with. With new tools or you know, like more effective tools. And now, of course, it's like we can try and of course to from our side the only way is to ensure. That, you know, like we routinely check, and we pass on information, and we ensure that everyone you know like we test the knowledge by asking questions, but you know like if. You know, like if any waiter or I mean if any, any, any crew would have any suggestion on how to improve. Of course, if it's something that is feasible, that's something we can implement while we are on board. Yes, we are open for feedback, and we try to see if it's something. That we can do otherwise if it's like suggestion related to something that you know, like my experience somewhere else where you know, like I just said, oh, and another company that used to give us like cell phones where, you know, like I was getting all my inbox and

whatsoever and they said Task I was getting over there, you know, this is something that is out. Of our hands. We cannot change it day in a Day, but we can Only pass on. This suggestion shows that, and they can consider if that is an investment that they can do for the company or Not.

How does this response impact the morale and job satisfaction of employees?

So if of course we are, we are able to implement something that has been suggested from the crew. It definitely gives, you know, like a very positive impact to the team, you know, a positive reinforcement where they feel integrated. And part of the team, they're actually you know like actively helping the team to succeed. It would be better. So, this definitely, you know, like empower, you know, like other people to do the same and empower, you know, to emulate, you know, like such action that, you know, it's for the final, you know, for the Bigger, good of for the entire company.

How does management currently approach the issue of safety culture In the company?

So of course, you know it's always a learning curve. We always try to understand what we can do better and it's, you know, like we unfortunately like human mistakes. You know, like you know everything we made, you know, like the only. Way for us is to continue and you know to make and then to practice like good habits and you know, to ensure that we don't, you know like fall, and we don't accept you know anything that is not you know like the right thing to do.

So of course, we need to ensure that we do the right thing, and we don't let anything slip through our fingers. So, we should always, you know, like never neglect anything that looks, you know, like not OK or not. But, you know, like always trying to understand if there is anything that we can do to solve the situation or like if the

situation is OK, you know like you know it's just OK or if it doesn't need any attention. So never you know like never Accept but you. Know to try to be always curious and to see if you know like everything is actually alright.

Have there been any past incidents that prompted the management to reevaluate their approach?

Yes, what I witnessed in the past is that we had a person that stowed away.

So basically, a person, you know, like during a drill that was conducted, a stow away, a person managed to sneak in on board because we were not scanning people getting off to speed up the process. We were not scanning people getting off To you know, to simulate a like an abandoned ship drill and then the people then were not scanned again to come on board, but they were actually, you know, like asked to proceed through security. Of course, you know, 380 and 60s crew.

And it was very difficult for security to spot any stow away. So one person managed to sneak in and managed to stay on board for more than four days before the person was, you know, like was recognized as somebody that has nothing to do either with guess and crew and of course that you know, like that was a very learning, your know, like a very big, you know concern, you know, like somebody could easily was able to easily get in and get on.

Luckily, the person didn't have any bad intention, but you know, like it could you Know could really. You know, affect everyone's safety on board and of Course from that moment, you know like.

They stopped that practice. They have to ensure that you know the right thing is done, so even if it's time consuming, they have to scan everyone off and in whenever you know like a drill is conducted, but most importantly, you know, like they need to ensure that everybody you know, like even on their time off, you know, they need to

either expose their ID or their name that certifies or at least you know give us the you know like the give us you. Know like the information that the person is, you know, I am crew member? Yeah. Ok

How does management incorporate feedback from crew in making decisions related to safety culture?

Well, you know, like we do believe that anyone's opinion is a, you know, it's worth it regardless of their position. So, it's, you know, doesn't matter if some. Feedback comes, you know, like from And New Academy or for my senior managers, you know, like we do believe that everyone has, you know, like the rights to say, you know, to speak up. But most importantly, anyone can, you know, like to raise any concerns and it doesn't come with experience. It comes just with You know, like we Just people noticing different things and you know. Having a different point of view and so of course it's We're doing kind of like open like for any kind of feedback and of course that's why sometimes we also have some safety tips. There is a safety tip box. You know that people can leave even anonymously, or you know, they can also put in their own information. So, it's a way, you know Like to, you know, to bring any concerns, you know, like up in case, you know, they might not be sure about something, or they might feel, you know like. I'm secure about something they can do. Do that and that is one way to collect feedback that we're doing, but also, it's like we know like despites for what it comes from. We actually evaluate if the feedback is, you know, like you know, it is worth to, you know like you know to be discussed or if it's something that has been discussed before. And you know, we already came up with a, you know, with a with a decision about it.

So how does management gather feedback from employees about communication and safety?

As I said before, Is a Dropbox Yeah, there is a Dropbox that they, you know, they people can. Do at any time and any Day, but we are routinely conducting, you know. Safety, you know. You know, like gatherings were. We actually discuss things I mean most commonly. You know, like incidents that can come That can happen on board And you know, these are called toolbox discussions where we actually kind of like share everyone's experience on, you know, how to properly conduct, you know our, you know our duties and how to ensure that everything is conducted on the same you know in safely and we kind of like don't you know like underestimate anything but we focus on everyone's health on board So during this you know, during this kind of like discussions.

We, you know, like to give the chance to interact and to share their own experience. And so that of course will Make everyone participate or you know like you know, very common scenarios of, for instance, could be like how you know how your back can be affected if you lift things in the wrong way or if you know, don't wear the proper shoe. You know shoes. Can it really affect your posture? And also, you know Like goes, you know, kind of like some other health related issues You know, if also it's the food where you know it's not adequate for the for the task that you know you're doing.

So again, during these sessions, you know everyone has a chance to kind of exterminate, you know, their own experience and any concerns they might have. This is a way where we can get feedback and discuss it. Otherwise, another way would be dropping you know Like a little suggestion to the inbox.

However, can you still share some or provide more examples of changes that have been implemented as a result of employee Feedback On safety and communication issues?

Oh well, you know, like, for instance, sometimes people like, even bikers, they might have noticed something, or they had, like, a personal incident and this could be like a sharp edge or like. A door that doesn't close Properly or instead of maybe it doesn't, you know, like a door that you know. Tends to, you know, like to band Too strong, especially strolls on the doors and walls are Very heavy, you know. 5 screen doors are a clear example.

They're very sturdy and heavy doors, and you know, and they are designed for that, but they have a slowing mechanism and, you know, in the engines, are you?

Know in design in a way that they have to close, you know, like in a safe way. And sometimes you know, like if people realize that the door is Shutting very too strong or another example like some of the working surfaces are too sharp and you know. The edges especially One still is involved, and you know still capsules. Removed and the edges are still rough and very sharp.

You know like and could cause legs and You know like. Could cause cuts or like tripping and not tripping. Kind of like hooking, you know, like somebody's uniforms. Then you know, they can easily report that to their supervisors. And of course, this, you know, escalated also To the, you know, safety officers, to show them. You know that you know like. You know, like the environment needs to be adjusted because it's not 100% safe. Of course, that you know like then you know it's gonna there's gonna be a log. In the record.

Any suggestion that the crew members made and of course the issue is fixed and we also do, you know, kind of share the information you know flip wide. To let you

know, let the people know that you know, like something that it Could be like A little small, you know, a hazard. Could have escalated on something bigger, but.

How does the Management prioritize and allocate resources for the initiatives aimed at improving communication and safety in the company?

As I said, like we have the tools, I mean we have the tools that I just mentioned before and when it comes to communication, you know like I said, like we do prioritize specific ways of communication.

If you know like, especially when safety related, the messages need to convey, we prioritize, you know, like of you know.

Like more. Direct way of communication so and so in this case. It's a phone call. You know, like creating immediate engagement with the person or live engagement with the person or, you know, like if it's, you know, if it's needed then also to send like kind of like a person just. Need to know. Do not send a message to somebody else. So more direct. You know, for something urgent and less, you know, like less direct. Such as an email for something that means that you can know. Can be kind of delayed. For snooze for a little bit later.

Last question, I don't know which company or cruise line you worked before, but can you share some best practices or success stories from other companies that have successfully implemented a culture of safety and how can this be applied in our company?

Well there, I have to say I'm. Things that we do not have that they have. Trying to think because. I don't have any other company experience. But if it's not, seaborne. Then I can, I mean it can. If it's not for Christmas, I can think of other companies that

I'll be working for and. I'm trying to think of. That we can plan to implement here that they have that we. Do not have. Well, I'm trying to think. Because we are, I mean, I kind of feel that the environment is safe. Already in a way that. We do have this kind of tool. And system design, you know, like for any inconvenience. Trying to think. Now, well, like for instance, like I noticed other companies, maybe sometimes 1 major issue is the grand way Right.

I have to say that I found sometimes way to be way too steep and then not, you know, like not friendly for most of our guests that are quite elderly and definitely, you know like one thing that I observed from other companies that they do keep trying to keep the gangway on the same level as the peer side where you know like it doesn't. Don't incentivize the use of this run or platforms that you know can cause you know, like discomfort or you know, like put somebody in danger. OK, I don't know if this is also well, I created some questions but. OK. How does the management response affect the Employees job satisfaction? Well, of course, if we do have a way to understand that our employees are not satisfied, then we need to understand which is the root cause for that. So, we need to definitely start an investigation, I mean we need to understand if the feedback is kind of like.

Kind of comes from the specific from a specific topic, or if it's general, whether we do know that the people are unhappy and then you mean like we need to understand which is the root cause and it will take quite some time , but definitely it's to again To a way to do it is just to ask and to kind of like ask for further feedback to more communication in a way of.

How do you know, like how? How? What do you Think is a major problem and how do you think we can? Improve it then.

In that case you know like we will let us know if you know. Like it's something that. So, if there is, you know, like already a solution for this problem, because sometimes again you know failing communication can lead to, you know, like crew not knowing that we might already have a solution for what they need. Is The problem, and sometimes it's just, you know, like again, you know like passing on the message or by explaining to them how to, you know like. How to solve the problem? Otherwise, you know, like you know, like it's always. You know, like good, you know to Understand if there is something that needs to Be done. To improve my lifestyle.

OK then and then how does the management communicate changes in response to employee's feedback regarding safety issues and how do employees generally respond to these changes?

So, we are again, we pass on you know like if there is a new change made and you know like and it's actually made by feedback you know from employees then of course we try to do it publicly and you know in a way that we want to reinforce the again this positive environment where you know they can contribute. And they are, you know, like, vital for, you know, for everyone you know, for the for the, for the, for the say, for the for the well-being of everyone's on board And of course, we want to kind of like, as I said, doing it, you know, in front of everyone that you know, like a single person contributed in the into the implementation of, you know, in to make any changes for the better or for the better for the, for the, for the better and the second part was again was.

And then how do employees generally respond to these changes?

Well, as I said, like you know, like it's they're very thankful. And of course, you know like we you know, we try to commemorate and to, you know like these milestones or not milestones these achievements with pictures and shared between, you know, between the fleet. So that gives of course again like a sense of pride. You know that. They did something very good and at the end, of course he will push them to do it again. Or inspire somebody else. To do it again, OK.

And then how does the management response to safety concerns impact Employees perceptions of their job security.

We are of course we are the one that needs to ensure that we pass on the information and the gravity of specific information. So it is important that we kind of engage the crew to have a clear understanding, you know, like of safety related issues or safety related Message and message that we need to pass on And how they are and why they are so important. So they, you know, like at the end of the day, we are here, you know, this is our work environment for everyone and they need to understand if something is not considered safe, it's, you know, it's for them to be able to either continue to do their profession, to do their job, but also to guarantee that.

Everyone has a job to, you know, to do, you know, has a, can preserve their job because at the end of the day, if you know, like we may, we can understand how this can affect the entire, you know, the entire well-being of everyone's work in a way that can either cause, you know, like stop of the operation if something is so serious that can stop, you know.

Like, I mean at the end of the day, safety could be anything.

Could be also, you know like to ensure that you know everyone is it's healthy and good but also like to not you know like do anything that can really compromise their health and the safety of whatever one could be like a fire or you know like a you know like of misuse of Electrical and equipment or either you know like. Like some equipment or the hardware equipment that can really harm somebody if it's not handled properly.

So, the fire of course is for everyone you know, like, you know, like, and they need to understand, you know, like it takes very little to go soon. You know, something very, you know, like they can spread very fast, and you know once you know like, you know, like the. You know such a thing as a fire, you know? Start to spread. You know, it can really, really put everyone in danger. And but, you know, ultimately, you know, like. Even if we had, we had drilled and you know like we try to do our best to, you know, to put everyone you know ultimately also the ship you know the ship will you know one way could you know Cease to exist and you know, and that would mean the end of everyone's job and career, of course.

And then how does the management respond to feedback regarding safety?

Regarding safety issues affect the trust that employees have in the company's leadership and that's what. Yeah.

How does the management response to feedback regarding safety affect the trust of the employees in the company's leadership and decision-making process?

Of course, if the employees don't see any feedback at all, that will, you know, discourage them. Them To bring anything up again. Or if they don't see that, you

know that their concern has been taken into consideration at all. They will feel like, you know, then you know, like they want to entrust their management for any other further communication. So it could be safety related or any other entity or communication, so they won't talk anymore. They will not talk anymore. They will close up or they will because at the end of the day they will. Do lots of waste of their time because they don't see any action taken and that way, they say no point to, you know, waste my time on bringing something up that I know that nobody's gonna take care of. Now take care of it.

So, it's important that of course that you know like I said before, regardless of who the person is or like how long has he been with the company or? He's, you know, his job position. We do, you know, take the time to acknowledge their feedback. So you know, like, if it's something that has been already addressed in the past or we do have an answer or solution for that, any particular concern you spend the time to explain it to the person. Otherwise, you know, like, show them, you know, like progression and, you know, like. If there is, like kind of. Like a discussion ongoing for one matter. Very last question, nothing.

Can you provide an example on how the management responds to a safety concern, impacted employees, job satisfaction?

So, I have to say safety. So, for instance, I remember in the past that we were told that for instance we like Polish glassware and Like of course using, you know, like using all rags. And what was happening is that like, sometimes you know, like people were getting cuts because of course, you know, like they couldn't see that some of the glassware was stripped.

So because they actually had to stick their hands, you know, like into the glassware and then friction that will, you know could have caused like some you know like did

cuts. Hi can I? Call you in a second. How urgent is your urgent? OK, so of course, you know the concern was brought up to the manager and they thought that there must be a solution to that. So change your way of polishing. You know the Glass work or either like giving some Extra tools, protective tools to the crew and of course, you know, like they implemented the you know like special. Gloves that anti cut gloves and you know would prevent. Of course, you know this from happening again. And that's of course you know, like the way that affected the crew is that before. People were reluctant to do that specific side job because you know, it's an incident in the. Past or they were either. Like, you know, paying extra attention, which you know. Of course, it's good for them to do, but they're slowing down. Of course, the operation because it would take a longer time to ensure that things are done properly. And of course, you know they were Not putting as much pressure as. That will was required for the polishing So with the new implementation instead, you know that will guarantee that you know grant to the crew that they feel safer, you know, to carry on with their duty to still, you know, like, feel like even if you know like equipment is cheap, you know, like they still feel protected and nobody you know was, you know, like stepping back from doing the duty.

And also the process of, you know, polishing glasses was actually improved by you know like you know like with the Faster, you know, like faster Execution and that of course felt, you know, like actually in. Create created a trend that when either when management was changing or like changing a different environment, different ship They you know Like they would, you know, like continue and request for, you know, the protective equipment, the quicker before from doing a job because they knew that they were, you know, he's available for them. So, they you know Create a

positive trend. And you know and pass on the knowledge to you. Know to the rest of the group prefect.

APPENDIX B

Interview of Crew B

CREW B RONNI

Ok, can you describe the general communication flow between the deck engine and hotel Services in Odyssey? Ibig sabihin pwede mo bang i describe ang kung anong klase ang communication meron ang Deck engine and ang hotel service? paano tayo nag uusap tatlong departamento (department) ? Ibig sabihin pwede mo bang i describe ang kung anong klase ang communication meron ang Deck engine and ang hotel service? paano tayo nag uusap tatlong departamento (department) ?

Through phone computers, and actual, Phone only on the phone. That's the most common OK, phone only.

How do the different departments coordinate with each other during operation? Paano raw yung tatlong departamento ng hotel deck and engine nang co coordinate during normal operation ?

Through radio, email, for example, Epicurean event is an event, . Paano nag uusap ang deck department, and marine, and ang hotel para maging successful ang event na yun ? Usually, it is given through advance email so there will be preparation.

Oo usually One day before, OK, at least? There is coordination.

Are there any specific tools or protocols in place to facilitate communication between these departments?

Can you describe any challenges or issues that arise from communication breakdowns between these departments?

For example, our supervisors have emails, but they don't tell us. That's the problem. Yes, because whenever there is an event, we cannot prepare for it properly. The issue there is when the information is not passed down to us properly.

How do the crew members on the vessels adapt to this communication dynamics?

Through training

OK, how does this dynamic of communication among the three organizations affect the culture of safety, safety of crews, of crews and guests onboard at Odyssey?

Communication through training, because in cruise ships the level of safety standard is very high. Almost every week we have safety training. Aside from crew training we also have additional training that is related to our department (electrical department) More technical safety like how to use ladders, we also have safety training for that, how to use harnesses in heights. Our boss talked to us about these trainings and not the safety officers. sometimes they talk to us sometimes they also invite safety trainers from outside.

What are the specific communication channels and ginagamit ng deck engine or hotel para makipag usap sa isat isa ?

In deck and engine, we have radio we also use phone and radio.

Can you provide an example of recent communication breakdown between these departments?

Maybe when there is no Internet sometimes when they send an e-mail, and we don't read it because there's no Internet. It's more on technical just like what you've said when there are communications from the supervisors, and it's not being passed out to us properly because of technical issues.

How does the lack of effective communication among the deck, engine, and hotel affect the safety culture on board ?

Yes, there are miscommunications there are times that they put something in the communication or email that's not needed. They put something in the email that's not yet needed.

The lack of effective communication affects the communication process because the tasks from the supervisors are not followed properly when there's a lack of communication you just talk but it's not effective. The communication passed down from the supervisors are followed but not all of it when there is a discussion about it.

Can you give any incidents where this lack of communication led to safety concerns for the crew and passengers?

For example, for technical reasons for wires and it's not being secured in the electrical department some experience trip some experience near miss slip because the instruction about safety was not communicated properly. There are times that wires are placed but it's not properly secured. I can say that the safety preparations are not enough because this incident probably happened when we were still preparing the stage and the guests were locked to an area where we haven't put

any safety precautions or safety barriers for walking or entering the place. It's more technical who instructed you to please wires in that place or location? Who is your highest supervisor in the electrical department? Is it the chief engineer or chief technician?

For example, it fits a request from the hotel department. Most of the orders come from the Chief technician. Not the chief engineer because it's a different department we do not receive orders from the chief engineer.

So, can you describe the management's response to feedback provided by employees regarding communication issues? So describe ang responde ng mga amo pag meron kayong mga feedback na nanggagaling sa inyo?

When there are communication and safety issues the management acts upon it immediately. We have daily meetings, and we talk about the problems that are happening and we provide solutions for them. We also try to provide solutions for these communication and safety issues. They listen to us.

Are they listening or not listening? They listen (in a very hesitant voice)

So how does this response impact the morale and job satisfaction of employees?

Of course, our morale becomes high because we know that we are being supported with the things that we need.

Do they listen to you most of the time?

They listen to us

Is there discrimination?

Discrimination is always there and cannot be avoided.

For example, when we request for proper shoes sometimes, right? it's expensive and costly. They just give us the cheap ones. They give more importance to economics or money, yes ha ha ha. It's a very big factory because the safety of the crew are being sacrificed.

How does management currently approach the issue of safety culture in the company?

Through Training. We have a lot of training such as flooding, we also have training for fires and others. We are also trained how to use firefighting equipment.

Aside from standard training do you still have any other training that are specifically done for your department?

how to use firefighting equipment.

Have there been any past incidents that prompted the management to reevaluate their approach? past incidents?

There are also incidents like that when you see one like networking improvement do you follow?

How does management incorporate feedback from employees in making decisions related to safety issues?

In my opinion yes in the electrical department, however they are scared right if you remember we have had an issue where we hired an environmental officer who helped the USPH. Before we don't a lot of position for public health no we now have a public health officer because of the feedback so they added this position because of the feedback right?

So how does the management gather feedback from employees about qualification and safety issues?

paano ba nakakakuha ng feedback ang management sa atin ?

We have a feedback mechanism where we can drop our feedback about health and guest issues. Is it effective?

I guess so

Can you provide some examples of changes that have been implemented as a result of employee feedback on safety and communication issues? Doon sa department ninyo ? Meron bang na implement na bago dahil sa result ng mga feedback ng mga sinabi ninyo ? May mga nadagdag ba na improvement

Yes there is we have now better tools for better safer.

What was the issue before ?

We have electrical tools before like screw drivers, it must be insulated, now we are forbidden to use open type screw drivers, its not insulated before and that's allowed but that's unsafe. But now, its not allowed anymore. So basically we have to adopt new safety measures

How does the management prioritize and allocate resources for initiatives Aim at improving communication and safety in the company ?

Just like what you've said, how do they prioritize your health and safety is through buying standard equipment related to safety

yes that's right, and I may also add that in ladders, we are not allowed to use aluminum ladders anymore, the ladder must be a plastic and not aluminum since we work for electric related concerns because aluminum are insolated and we might get electrocuted because of an electrical accident. The electric current will not flow if the ladder is plastic

Can you share some best practices or success stories from other companies?

That have successfully implemented the culture of safety?

hindi ka naman nagtrabaho sa ibang company no?

Yes there is but in the Philippines it's not that good when it comes to safety

How does management response affect the employee's job satisfaction?

paano daw kapag ang management ay nagbigay ng responde na maayos, nakakaapekto ba to sa job satisfaction ?

yes definitely it is easier to work when you know that you are safe and you don't have any safety issues

How does the management employ feedback regarding safety issues ?

we have weekly training related to safety. even though it may sound repetitive but it is about safety first. for example how to use a line. There are times that we are adamant to follow or do the but when you think of it it's for your own good you still need to follow

Are you hesitant to do it ?

yes sometimes I think it's overkill on our side. It may be unnecessary because I've been working in the cruise ship industry for 10 years and we haven't encountered any accidents or safety incidents before. But we still do it because it's the protocol

So how does the management response to safety concerns impact employees perception of their own job security?

it's the same because just like what I've said when you know that you are safe and when you know that you're being supported by the company by providing what you need

How does the management response to feedback regarding safety issue affect the trust that employees have in the companies leadership and decision making process?

Kunyari nag respond na yung management natin sa sinasabi ng crew, regarding sa safety affect the trust that employees have in the company's leadership and decision making process

Because of the managements proper response to safety issue, I love the company even more because you know it's a given big process you know the feeling that are being supported.

Can you provide an example of how the management responds to a safety concern, impacted employee job satisfaction?

Just like what I've said before for example when the company gives us the standard tools and equipment related to safety

Appendix C

Interview - Crew C

Can you describe the general communication flow of the three department of the ships?

A department like engine and deck and FNB. Mostly they talk about They can communicate with their supervisor, like as a waiter, if I have something to ask from engine, I ask first with my immediate supervisor. So my immediate supervisor will talk to them. OK, that's how it works for my position. For my position it goes to my supervisor. Yes, I go first to my supervisor. If I need something from them.

How do the different departments, deck engine, and hotel coordinate with each other during operations?

They are using phones . First, first of all they are using phones or e-mail or personal information. Talk with each other. So the department heads talk to each other.

Sometimes, yeah. Or yeah, we cannot. We cannot ask for. Like like the deck is dirty. We cannot ask for straight to the deck department to clean it. We must ask first to our supervisor to tell them to. Clean it. Something like that. That the situation with the communicate with their supervisor of the department. OK. And that in the supervisor will communicate to the supervisor of that.

Are there specific tools or protocols in place to facilitate the communication between the three department?

As a waiter I have a senior waiter to tell first, then my senior waiter will tell the supervisor then to the manager until. OK. And then they communicate. So there's like a hierarchy.

Can you describe any challenges or issues that arise from a communication breakdown between different departments?

About the issue for me, challenges for me sometimes. Between department, yes, special no. About engine and deck and FNB, there's not too much. Too much challenges. In operation because. Because we're different operational system, you know. But what if the three departments is about? They are in one event, how it will become a challenge for How? How it will become a challenge for you. For example, if deck engine and FNB for example, we have a period, how these three departments or for you for example, how do you face the challenges with that kind of event?

Have you experienced any challenges?

Actually, I don't have experience any challenges, different communication challenges between other department as a waiter.

The communication between OK. If I get challenges with them, I just pass it to my supervisor. Period. Supervisor. So basically the challenges are like more on the supervisor, OK,

How do crew members on the vessel or in the Odyssey adapt to this communication dynamics?

They give us a training about higher key about how can we communicate with other department. They give us training that if there was a issue about other department is not our responsibility to address it it will be the responsibility of our superior. To address the issue.

What specific communication channels do the deck engine and hotel service?

To each other.

What specific communication channels channels do the deck, engine, and hotel services For each other or what do they use to communicate to each other?

We got phone on board phone. We got a e-mail like aimes if we got some something broken. In our area. We can aim. To e-mail the repair personnel. How does how does a lack of effective communication among the different department affect the safety Culture on board.

How does a lack of effective communication between the three departments affect the safety culture on board?

It's very bad, although we don't have good communication with each department because sometimes, we have a safety protocol on board, which is if we are not communicating, we cannot. If we are not communicating well, there could be a

hazard for everyone. OK, so it's very important to have. Yeah, like when we are tendering, we're doing. For your department. Fueling the ship then our department, we've been called by the deck department, the deck department called the FNB Department to close our smoking area, which is part of our department. The tables for smoking area. The deck department calling us. Calling the FNB department to close the smoking area when it's tendering, they'll be doing the ship. If they don't. Call you. It will be a safety issue. We don't know where. Yeah, it's gonna. Be a safety issue. So basically, it should be related.

Can you describe the management response?

Yes, something like that is not a solution To feedback provided by employees regarding communication issues.

Can you describe the management response to feedback provided by employees regarding communication? Can you describe the management response to feedback provided by employees regarding communication issues?

Have you ever given Feedback to your managers and your manager and what's your manager's response to it?

Regarding your work or any safety matters, what do you normally get from your managers? What kind of response do you have? You normally get.

Normally, when about the safety and hazard issue. They give us training about it so they don't need to keep telling us what is safe And what is not?

But how about in your work if You give something Regarding your work Do they act accordingly?

They act accordingly by the book. They cannot act accordingly because it's no good as well for our moral like they criticize us.

Like I we got an issue of safety and hazard and they, they caught us doing some dangerous stuff. They Tell us. OK, but sometimes we shortcut so. Yeah, problem it's a problem.

How do this Response impact the morale and job satisfaction of employees?

So how does your managers response impact the morale and your job satisfaction as an employee?

If you could some it's sometimes it's good to be criticized and to be tell what is wrong and right. Sometimes it's good to to remind us. And it's good for our moral as well. So, the next time we planning to do shortcuts or Not the hazardous thing. We're aware of it. Thank you.

How does management currently approach the issue of safety?

As I said earlier, they always giving us a training about the safety culture on board. OK, so.

How does the management gather feedback from crew members about communication and safety issues?

How does the management Responds to feedback. How does the management response to feedback affect?

Each decision to adopt the culture of safety.

So how does the management respond to feedback Affect each decision to adopt the culture of safety because again.

Ibig sabihin may sinabi ka sa manager Mo Regarding safety issues. Papaano siya (ito) . Nakakaapaekto sa kaniyang decision As a manager, yung culture ng safety. Is it straightforward, straightforward ba siya ? Wala ba siyang pagtatakpan ? How does the management response (papano daw mnagements response to feedback affect

its decision to adopt the culture of safety? Halimbawa may sinabi ka sa manager mo
finoolow up mo, walang ginawa, paano makakaapekto sayo to ?

To adopt the culture of safety, how does the management response to adopt the
culture of safety? It's very it could affect my emotional moral. And mental health as
I know, because you know, it's feel like it's unfair as a crew That's not fair. OK. Uh
huh?

have you experienced personal incident that you were ignored and the management
didn't act upon your feedback?

I've got my issue Have you experienced anything as my career grow, I've never
experienced that kind of issue because I've never had Any issue with my colleagues
with my crew?

With my other crew.

So, it means your it means your manager. All your managers always respond to your
feedback.

I never complained a lot something like that.

No, but what I mean have you experienced? Have, were there any managers that
when you have?

I experienced that issue when I in my first contract I address a person that doesn't
finish all his job to prepare for me in the morning, OK. To prepare for me in the
morning. Then I ask for my it's not a manager, it's a major ****. Uh means like a
supervisor. But this person is This person ohh. But this person is friends with the
guy I was telling him. And then you just laugh. At me, OK. It's that time I was a utility,
so the one that I am complaining is. Another waiter. But this guy and the other guy
is long-time friend, so they disregard my issue. They just laugh at me and then they
still push me to finish it. He didn't do anything. Even it's not my job which is supposed

to be the other person to finish, to finish those job. And 1st it's Jim. I feel yeah. And it's felt bad to me. But then as a crew member and you know, as before, it's really sad, but it's true. Unfortunately, it Happens. It happens, unfortunately. The media said that we Filipino have been treated differently with other nationalities. That's fine because we will.

Can you provide some examples of changes that have been implemented as a result of employee feedback on safety and communication issues on board? Have you? Could you provide some examples in the ship if there are any changes on the safety regulations that have been changed and implemented as a result? Of your, for example of a result of our employee's feedback or comment. Were there any changes you know? Yeah. For example, in your, in your work in your work area Have there been any.

It changes. Yeah, that changed of some of the area or something like that like Suggestion or feedback Yeah. For example, for example like Glass. What kind of the glass that you use?

Yeah, it happened. I think in Like in a in a club area in Liverpool side. In the neck pipe up. Club Whirlpool side, you know that outside your pool people were using glass like a real glass. Beside the Whirlpool, but then the safety safe because of safety. OK, because of They push to use only plastic.

OK, so that's the effect of a feedback coming from an employee for safety issue. So, the management act upon it is OK that's good. So that's good. So how does?

Yes, yes, yes, yeah.

How does the management prioritize in allocating resources for initiatives aimed at improving safety communications in the company?

The management prioritize in allocating resources for initiatives aimed at improving communications and safety in company, how does the managing management prioritize and consume its money, its resources, to making sure that the safety is the top priority?

The company schedule us for training OK for safety training, which is they pay our hours, they pay, they pay the person who train us their hours. That is, I think what they resource the resources used to for our safety, for everyone, safety, employee safety.

You share some best practices or success from other companies like in the Philippines. Have you ever worked aside from the Odyssey or Seaborn that you worked before, that you know that successfully implemented a culture of safety? And how can this be applied to Seaborn? Are there any good safety measures in your previous company that you think that can be adopted, adopted here and what is that?

Let me think about it. It's. My previous company is hotel. I think about security. About security like, they're very strict about security, about the, about the crew. About there was no. There's no backup, you know. What can I say this? for example, I work in celebrity cruises. Yeah, in seaborn. Because of safety and security. Security, safety also. In celebrity cruises everywhere you go, there's a lot of cameras. Yeah, that's what I'm thinking about here. To see all this, there's not too, too much CCTV here. Numbers. Yeah. CCTV cameras to review for any reference for any incident or any security or any related accident. Yeah. Incident matters.

How does the management communicate changes in response to employees Feedback regarding safety issues and how do the employees respond to these changes?

The management communicate the changes in response to employees' feedback, I think. They must choose first which one is the best. To apply in safety in every crew, because not only one person will suggest what is the best for the safety of everyone. So, I think they must choose what is the best, because you cannot apply everything. So basically, any feedback that they gather from the Crew, they do, they study it? Do they study all this feedback? Do they read all of them? Your management is OK. They Study first if it's applicable. Yeah, something like that. Supposed to be they cannot. They cannot apply every crew suggestion.

How does the management response to safety concerns impact employees' perceptions of their own job security? So how do employees? How do you as an employee get impacted Regarding the management response to safety?

It's good for us. It feels like we're really part of the (community) Our voices are being heard, something like that.

OK, so if the management is not doing anything about safety?

It's gonna be like this is not a good company. The management is not doing the Where it's not. It's very biased. Something like that. If it's because they're just an employee, they will not hear your complaint.

So does your management right now, do they respond to safety concerns?

Yeah, currently my management is there.

They're listening. Our concern. I experienced this before because of the discrimination we experienced as a Filipino employee. It happens as it did when my first contract. Like I was telling earlier that there was a supervisor, which is his in the other company now. The Supervisor who I told me my concern, but the supervisor is friends with this guy, so he just laughed at me and then he continued to give me

a hard time to push me to do the other guy's task, which is always drunk. Never been sober. Something like that every night.

And then how does the management response to feedback regarding safety issues affect the trust that employees have in the company's leadership decision making process. So how does the management respond to your feedback? For example, how does your manager's response to your feedback regarding safety issues affect your trust in the company's leadership and decision making process?

It really affects me. It really affects my morale, my mentality, my emotions. As an employee, I always think it's my personal mindset. It's my personal mindset that I'm just an employee. I'm just a number, so if they don't then I just continue my job. It's my personal mindset, you know, it's, I don't know if other will agree with me, but then it's my personal mindset that if they don't hear my concern, then I'll just continue what I am doing as an employee.

OK. Can you provide an example on how the management responds to safety? Impacted the employee job satisfaction. Can you provide an example on how your manager's response to safety concerns impacted your satisfaction, your job, your job satisfaction? Have you experienced any? When when? Yeah, you have said a while ago and that's the same. Have you noticed how OK. Have you noticed how the department communicates?

I'm not sure about it because I never talk with them, mostly my superior. But when you? Observe when they talk and communicate. They talk as normal but. Can you see the difference on how when you ask them about a job, it's always like, oh, this is my only, this is the Only thing you must do. Yes, of course there are the limited job descriptions like they have. They are limited. They always, especially when they are in the area of FNB which is a restaurant. They always ask if we can, we can start

the job. Our job now in this area or not or what time we can start like in a bar, in a bar, in a patchy bar. The engine department, which is the repair, what you call this. The ice cream ice cream freezer they always ask when they can start So basically the deck and engine department are very straightforward. When they work they have, like you know, they work 8:00 o'clock and they stop at. 10:00 o'clock automatically because the time is 10.

Yeah, they're very strict with their time, right?

Yes. And, when they communicate, they. Unlike the service, because in service in FNB department. When the person they have flexible. Yeah. If the person stays at 3:00 AM, we stay. Which makes up all your time at 3:00 AM, yeah.

Yeah, but for the engine department once, no.

For the engine department, they don't have. They don't have guests, they don't have. They're not dealing with the. This is the right. They're dealing with, I guess. They're not. They're not dealing with the guests. They're just dealing with the with the stuff, with the destruction, the.

Have you, have you? Have you noticed when they are talking? When when it comes to work, they when they talk, they are very, very limited. They're very straightforward. It's they will tell you it's not my job. Or you have to tell this to my boss because it's that part of my job today. Yeah. Yeah. Because everything needs to be scheduled for them. They don't. They don't do. They don't do extra.

They are not flexible every day.

Services for the hotel department if you ask them something. If they can do it right away, they can do it without. Aims. Yes, correct. So, see. So that's the difference.

The last difference is the dynamic communication between. Engine, deck and hotel. What's the difference? And the difference between the dynamic communication with the Hotels and the When you communicate to each other.

We do, we do communicate but. As for them, the engine and deck. They do their job; they do their job by schedule. By the paper the difference between us is we do the job. As a hotel representative. We do the job Straight away. Yeah, No questions asked. We give what we have, but we never say no. We never say no. No. So if the guest says, If the guests ask for kangaroo meat, let's say kangaroo meat, because before we have kangaroo meat, let's say that. If the guests ask for kangaroo meat, then we never say no to the guest. We will say to the guest we will double check if we still have.

Also, with regards to safety, sometimes safety issues are already hazardous and risky, but you want to give guests guest satisfaction. You normally get a hotel will just call this neglect? Just to have guest satisfaction, right?

You know why? Just for example. This is now for the Entertainment department. It rained last night. Right. But for guest satisfaction. It is for, but for dissatisfaction I train you to have electricity. So, the electricity of the, the electrical, the electrical equipment got wet and then it causes a lot of noise, a lot of noise and also the band do not want to work anymore. Right. They do not want to play because they said it's hazardous. The cables are all wet, it's all electrical and wet, wet water and electricity cannot combine. However, the hotel manager insisted. To keep it going. And then he even called the housekeeping department. To try to dry it. Get, get a blower trying. Keep trying and then we keep still hearing the noise and he still keep telling. No, no, no. It will be OK. It will be so. He grabs all the housekeeping department. He made everybody mopped the floor. He asked the FBI manager to run from deck to

deck. 3:00 to Go with the division Get all the get the converters good. Get everything to make it work. But yeah, but everybody's already telling it's wet. We cannot continue. Just for yeah, just for. Because it's hazardous, it's hazardous. It's risk. But the hotel. Manager because of guest satisfaction as what you said, he just wants to satisfy the guests. And now safety. Person the safety of the crew members and the team members became at risk or in jeopardy. Because of what the hotel manager wants? Because he wants to have a good job. Just he wants to have a good guest satisfaction. So that's the difference. OK, thank you.

APPENDIX D

CREW D

Tony, what's your name and your position in the ship?

So, my name is Tony Barwell. I'm the ship safety officer.

Can you describe the general communication flow between the deck, the engine, and hotel services? Can you describe the general communication?

So I mean, you've got everyone under the captain, different hotel director, staff captain, chief engineer or head of the department. I guess that's the main route of communication, OK, but obviously as people are working with each other. Directly we communicate directly. Mid management level.

How do the different departments or how do the different departments coordinate with each other during operations?

I guess this other one is necessary just through the supervisors. Obviously for me, as a safety officer, if I have an issue with. So, for example, entertainment, I'll go and speak to either the cruise director, assistant cruise director or production manager. Yeah, depending what it's on. Either via e-mail, which is useless mobile phone, or it's a small ship you walk and go and speak to the person.

Are there any specific tools or protocols in place to facilitate communication between these departments?

So, I guess it's not necessarily. It's not communication in talking, but we have things like aims, you know, for raising that. You know it's a way of communicating. OK, AIMS is the device, or an application used for the work order. So, there's an issue on board you raising aims using the app and that then sends it through to say you make it for the repairman or a Carpenter and he goes from that phone.

Can you describe any challenges or issues that arise from communication breakdowns between these three departments?

Quite a lot of times, or particularly if it's through written communication or by e-mail or something very easy to get misinterpreted or misunderstood. Again, you've got people whose second language is English. Just me, the simple thing is when things aren't being understood properly, go down and talk to the person and go and see them both go to the place where whatever the issue is, is and look at it together, and usually that clears up very quickly. But yeah, second language English and using written communication does not face to face.

How do the crew members on the Odyssey adapt to these communication dynamics?

Doing well, but most people are very experienced, so we know how. To me speaking English is the first language I know. Sometimes I have to slow down. Yeah, repeat it. You know, use different terms. Just to get the message across, because again it's second language English so. In some ways, we can almost develop our own little language. Yeah, like for example, I just said aims earlier on, I just say aims and I expect people to know what aims. Is because it's, yeah. You know those

acronyms, those that were? It's almost like a shipboard slang like this. So, it's a, it is a shipboard communication. Yeah. Like using. Yeah, yeah.

So how does this dynamic of communication among the three organization, deck engine, and hotel affect the culture of safety of crew and guest on board.

It's a good one. Safety usually comes on the deck department. Yeah, I'm the safety officer. One thing I don't like of it is, and it feels like everyone is expecting the safety to be handled by the safe jobs and by the deck department when it's not, it's a universal thing It's relatively good. The safety on board, but I think a lot of people lean heavily on to. The date Department to provide for safety, OK. Depending on their experience or some people are pretty good, especially new people, they. Want things done for them?

So, what specific communication channels do the deck, engine and hotel services use to interact with each other?

So, it's apart from that the Wi-Fi. Phones and emails AIM. Talking to each other, can you provide an example of a recent communication breakdown between these three departments. Was there any experiences or examples That had happened in the past?

Again, go back to emails. They're not great. An e-mail you sent a certain time. You're requiring the person who sent it to them. There's a delay in them then reading it. If something they don't have to action. For example, crew trainings. In Vancouver on the 11th, I sent an e-mail for train the next day too late because I've. Been busy with an inspection. So normally I send it in the morning, but now I sent it. In the early evening, so a lot of the staff didn't see it till even later on. When they went back into. The offices then they tell the crew members who got trainings in the next morning. I've got lots. Of crew that are not the training because they they were

told so late. So that's. Every got to be pre planned. If you pre planned too much. And so, we in Vancouver, you get surprised inspection and the whole day gets moved around.

So how does the lack of effective communication among these three departments affect the safety culture onboard?

What's the recent example. I think it's just like misunderstandings or like. But that's misunderstanding, but. So, the Commission say we get a new procedure, some of those takes a lot to explain it to people who. Have never seen that procedure before. And for him to understand it, like for me as a deck officer, I've been surrounded by safety on. My career, when you have someone to take housekeeping, example, a cabin cleaner, a suite attendant can step up to assistant housekeeper and they have to learn all these procedures, all these different things That they never dealt with before. It can take a lot so. Yeah, so the lack of it needs to have an effective communication for it to work, because if there's lack of effect, effective communication between. Yeah, because if someone new to position, they need support and they need help from experienced people. So, they need a way of easy communicating with those people that do have the knowledge. While they learn it.

Can you share any incidents in your experience, where there is lack of communication Led to a Safety concern for the crew and guest?

Usually for me the worst reason we have. Heavy loading heavy loading, so lots of stores coming on board, whether it's, you know, food provisions or it's spare parts. You know the office will send all this equipment to the ship and then there's no communication. This goes beyond just the ship this goes to The office as well. There's no communication into the ship and then. Between different departments of exactly what everybody's got arriving. So, there's no pre plan where it will be stored.

It all just comes on Board and on that day, we've got to find someone to put it on. So then you end up with corridors, storerooms. Just completely full of stores Which needs to be clean Which needs to be cleared because it's it's blocking escape routes, it's blocking firefighting access to be clear So when I find it, I report it and it gets Dealt with quickly. But it would never happen in the 1st place if we had a proper plan for where this stuff would be And it goes into that.

If we can't store it, we turn to the company and say you. Need to reduce this order? You know what? It never happens, but that's what I was discussing a few Days ago I Said we can't store, or we book out a cabin and we use that as a temporary storage or something. You know, there has to be a proactive plan. A compromise, not a reactive plan. You know, because OK. Some department that's old store this so they find something to store it and then I go down there with safety and go. You can't store it like that because in their head their job is to store something. In my head safety. I walk into a store and manage to see enough space. If I need to get a fire team in there. The detectors that the sprinklers and that all going to work properly. Sometimes crew members, when they have their job to restore it, they forget they all know about the storage doors, but they forget about it because they're supervised, or the head of department is saying you need to put this away somewhere else and that becomes their new priority and safety sort of drops.

So, which one which one is the priority Safety or safety. Always safety, safety. But it always must be like because the one day that us. But there was like instances that the safety was compromised because some of the Hotels need needs to be Yeah, the, the, the locker in the grand salon in the last few days. If you saw inside the one next door Booth completely full of boxes of jackets and parkers. So, you

can't open the door So if there had been a fire in there, we can't get the fire Team in there. To to put it out, we're just gonna must seal off the area. And let it there's no. Yeah, stop it spreading so we can't. I don't think it's going to generally endanger the ship because we really contain it in the area. It in that. Area, but we wouldn't be able to put it out. It's going to be A long process of just boxing in the first Seeing the fire whilst it burns.

Yeah, that's a That's a good example.

Can you describe the management which can you describe the managements response to feedback provided by crew members regarding communication issues?

That got fixed straight away by the way, when I put it up Very much depends on the management, who's there at the time. Again, depending on their experience and their personality, some are a lot more open to it than others. The general culture, I would say, is open to feedback. But there are some but there are some that are still. Take it like personally. Not as he personally, but they just say this is the way it's always been done. That's where we do it. You know, so unless it's like a glaring gaping procedure or gaping safety, usually people like to stay. With what they've done before, OK, so. That's the safe. That's the safe side. But sometimes to change something, you can make it safer. Just we've done it one way before. Doesn't mean there isn't another way, which is more efficient Safer. Yeah, so.

So, having said that, how does this response impact the morale and job satisfaction of employees?

If you get a positive response and you see that your suggestion is taken forward, that's a huge morale boost for anyone because it's easier to take Everything you're valued. If you feel like they don't listen to, they just say yeah. That's very nice

and then move on. If it demoralizes you and you won't make more suggestions. So, it's really important safety culture. If someone has a suggestion, you listen to it. If you think that's a good idea, you implement it, and if they see it implemented, or if it's not, or there's some reason we can't. Do you explain to them why?

One, were there any instances that you know your experience that there were from Members who gave some feedback, but they were It was denied or was not it was ignored?

Yeah, I mean, it happens quite honestly, it's denied or ignored if. It's denied. It's Usually denied for a reason, but because for a. That's when you Have a problem, because then that crew member probably won't come forward with Anything else again. So, we we have this the suggestion box which is very really thought out by crew. They can write down a suggestion on there. I then checked it I Looked at it if it's a good suggestion, would implement it. Over the course of a month, the best suggestion Can win in the Hess Award the prize. Which again is trying to nurture that and encourage people to come forward is to have a suggestion is.

So how does management currently approach the issue of safety culture in the company?

Honestly, they don't. There's, like, they just kind of Think it's there and then when there's a problem, it's very reactive in my opinion or What I've seen, they they wait for it to be a problem and then they respond to it. And we try to improve things So quite often we're Again, yeah, we've been reactive and not proactive things, and we wait till oh that's wrong and then we work it out. And quite often depending on the department. You'll see an improvement for a week or so and then it will drop away again, so it Yeah, there's no consistency. Sometimes it it depends exactly what it is It depends on what we implement.

Have there been any past incidents that prompted the management to reevaluate?
Where have there been any past incidents that prompted the management to evaluate the approach in safety?

Titanic got to Concordia On board, yeah. Every there's been no, like, massive change of how we approach something Right. It still uses the same sort of route you've been using. I think that I think it works, I think. Our safety on board is pretty good. It's just making sure that we encourage grooms in the right way. To keep doing it automatically, don't have to wait to be told, they just do it automatically. Proactive, not reactive. Still working? Yes, I'm still working.

How does management incorporate feedback from employees in making decisions related to safety culture?

So, the official rule is we have to have an action Team meeting. So you have your representatives Reminds me there needs to be a new representative OK, that should go to the hat meeting Anything from the hat meeting should then go to the Has action Team Steering Committee, which is the Senior Matter Board Captain, Staff Captain, hotel director and chief engineer and environmental officer there as well So their feedback should go through that route to them.

Then how does the management gather feedback from employees about communication and safety issues?

They're gonna be that, that meeting Yeah, that would be the and all that gets all, all those meetings going to minutes and are sent to the company. So, it even goes above the ship level.

How does the management response to feedback affect each decision to adopt A culture of Safety Board?

They're gonna, if they're not reacting, if they're not seen to be Improving what's brought up by crew members, the safety culture would just drop off and people would lose interest and say it doesn't matter what I say. Nothing's gonna change, yeah If there seem to be proactive. And crew members will start to come forward.

Can you provide some examples of change that have been implemented on board because of crew members, feedback on safety and communication issues?

This one is not to be implemented yet It's in process crew member. We have our safety questions that we. Give up to all crew, yeah. She came up. She's an ex-teacher. She's got teaching experience. You pointed out how the way that our questions are laid out, they're kind of jumbled up different places. It's not very easy to read or use format. So now she's working on that to improve it, using her experience as a teacher once she's done with that, that question sheet should be OK. Given out to then all the crew maybe not as good, but even all the other ships in Seaborn in that format, which would be easier to use, so same with. It can be simple things like remember, just spot something that I think could be a hazard and say that was painted with the black and yellow paint highlights. It's a danger. The next week, they say it's been done painted. It's kind of happening frequently, like even this morning before I left the ship, there was a chef came with the idea of putting some non-sticky the tape, the non-slip tape. In one of the galleys because he said, well, I'm here, I can sometimes slip. I said to tell the new safe job to come back to leave, but yes, it's a good idea. We'll just get it in.

Then how does the management and the ship prioritize and allocate resources for the initiatives aimed at improving communication and safety on board?

Changing the actual communication routes. That kind of has to go. Through head office. OK, for example, that Is a defect on why something wrong? It's gonna go through AIMS. We can't change games. That's the tool we've been given by. There's nothing on board we can do to Adjust how that works Yeah, there's not really, we. We work with a set framework that the company gives us, OK.

But can you share some best practices or success stories That you work from other companies That have successfully implemented for a culture of safety on board and how can this be applied to the ship, to our ship?

And experiences from the past company that we can implement on. The ship with two previous comes I worked for before Seaborn We're not great with safety, so it's a container ship company and then a wind farm boats in the North Sea and OK Not the people we employed. Some have no clue. So, it should be even better here. Yeah, yeah, I see it's taken more seriously here.

How does the management response affect the employees job satisfaction? Hugely It's a matter of valued again Is that sense of being valued and that your opinion matters and as soon as you have that you're following the news If there is a new procedure implemented because you've suggested it, you will follow that procedure because it makes more sense to you with. Someone doing the job? Yeah, then you're more likely to bring forward more suggestions because you know you're taken seriously. Yeah, it's just that Working as a team and not just Blindly following, you know it's. There's a book. What does the phrase they use inside the book put turn the ship. Around the book. About changing this culture on a submarine. Yeah. So instead of it. Being leader follower, it's leader. So, everyone is doing their own job, knows how to do it. I suggest him how to do it well and then the leader at the very top doesn't really have. To do much because it's all happening lower down.

And how does the management communicate changes in response to crew members feedback regarding safety issues?

So the visual channel again is in The hat meeting It should go Back it's posted the minutes get posted.

On the board It should also go back through the representatives for each department. They should feed it back down to. The crew as well.

How do the employees generally response to these changes?

I never really find. Out there's usually there's the IT gets closed. An outstanding thing on the Minutes and then we never actually speak directly to the crew ourselves.

How does the management respond to safety Impact employees' perceptions of their own job security

So, our job security mean like future employment.

How does the management response to feedback regarding safety issues affect the trust that employees have in the company's leadership and decision-making process?

Obviously, people want to feel safe, especially working on a ship environment. If you feel like the senior management, the captains, staff captains, your heading department, yeah, aren't competent, aren't good at their job You're not going to feel safe. You know, we've all seen disaster movies about ships, yeah. can you provide an example of how the management responds to a safety concern, impacted employees job satisfaction?

Me if I get taken seriously. If I bring up a suggestion and that session gets taken forward implemented And again just adding that value to while you're there It's every blindly following instructions. You've got to start the reason why do we do

something? This is what we do because we're told to we do it this way because in an explanation so. But but uh, in on the ship.

What kind of communication really do we have because The deck Department, when you talk and when you communicate, it's not the same as the hotel. Hotel seems to be relaxed, you know they can, they can. You know anything that is Sometimes they break rules just to give guests satisfaction. But does this get satisfaction? And on the deck department side. In the cruise ship. How how this one like your safety? Because like it's more on safety, right? The tech department you are like safety oriented, yes. Guest is more on guest satisfaction oriented.

So, but ultimately, I think we do have to be safe. So, remember as well from the bridge we come with deck offers become as navigation officers. So, when we're navigating the ship, all our communication has got to be understood So we use closed loop communication. So, you give an order you want just repeated, you say yes it was understood. So, it's not, I want to say it's military, but it's that kind Of like rigid style of how we communicate. But it sounds like a Billy. It sounds like a it's sort of like a military style, right? Yeah, it?

Less, more relaxed than the military. But yeah, it we follow a separately. And our job is purely to make sure the ship is safe. We're gonna be assessed on that by inspections like Coast Guard or Port State control in other countries, they're gonna come aboard and check our ship. There shouldn't be any gray area of like. Oh, it's it's OK if it's like this if we keep. This living in the storage room, would you keep like? That for a couple. Yeah, no, it needs to be moved as soon as possible because. You never know when it's gonna be an emergency. So even for half an hour to leave something in a dangerous state. If in that half an hour something happens. How do you explain? Why have you left by that? So, for example, we have near misses if

there's something seen, it could have potentially been a hazard. That gets put out as a report and shared with the rest of the fleet. The friend learned people like the big one is fire screen doors being blocked, doors which can shut and protect the ship, stop smoke spreading. Some crew member puts the other day was a bag of garbage in front of our screen door. Puts it there. And walks away. Maybe they were gonna come back in 10. They're gonna leave it there the whole night. Don't know, but I came down at that time and saw it take a photo for the report. And I immediately move it out of the way so that equipment can operate. Yes, for guest satisfaction, sometimes we're a little bit flexible. With procedures for relating to the Hotel department. But when it comes to safety there. Should be no. No flexibility. And if there is there needs to be some kind of Risk assessment, some kind of understanding OK. If we're going. To do this, how much higher is the risk going? For example, one viewer actually. You call us twice. The detectives in the grandson. So we're shutting down safety equipment, yeah. The reason we're doing that is because the show we're smoke so, but we know that you guys are there for the whole time and can raise your arm on our behalf. It's on a timer so you guys cannot accidentally leave on over overnight. So, when you leave it. Shall I go back to zero or if you forget, it's gonna turn itself back on shortly after. Then the show. Can you isolate it for one hour? And the show. Is going to be that time. So again, we're. Taken away a safety device, but we have steps implemented to make sure that the fire detection area is taken over by a person if the fire detection system goes down, some on the ship due to a technical fault, we implement a fire patrol and somebody walking around the area, so. If you do something to compromise safety, you have to put some other kind of measure to make sure the risk hasn't gone too high.

Do you think that there will be in the future A sort of a sort of a kind of Nautical Language Like in a cruise ship because right now it's like, you know, I do not know.

I don't know what kind of what kind of kind of language or communication Like for example you said. Aims is sort of like ships. So the thing in the future there will be a lot of ships. Aims, aims style of communication I think because they seem to go more and more Towards apps and devices. So, I guess in Yeah, I think it'll always be. Yeah, because the guests do not know aims. But when the crew members talk to each other and you talk to me and in front of the guests, you're talking about aims. And the guests like what seems yeah. But even that sort of thing is true. Like you know, it's. A lot. Bananas and You know there's already a sort of shipboard language explained among the crew. What are other shipboard languages that we normally use, aside from aft. Yeah, but even just, I mean it's many anagrams. Things only people on ship understand. OK. Got pH and no one says public health, but you see ph. Everyone knows what it means. So, it's always these. So, these are like the language on the ship, right? These are like the that most people are like, you know, when you talk about, you know that they are working on the ship because they know this kind of language. I'm sure it's the same in here in Apple, I'm sure this. The staff here communicate with each other using shorthand and phrases Is that we're like, what does that mean? But they immediately known. Because I don't. I don't think there's still there is a study about ship communication. That pertains only to cruise ship. That's specifically that we understood amongst us. That we created amongst ourselves. So those are the communication that we do on board, yeah, so.

Appendix E

Narrative Report of Sandy Bayas regarding the safety issue in his cruise ship.

My personal observation regarding safety and crew satisfaction is based on my personal experience. I'm from the Ent department and we normally set up musical instruments poolside which is open.

Before the pandemic the stage poolside has a canopy as a protection to all band and electronics and electrical equipment set up from sudden rain. It also serves as a shield to sun rays for those performing in the middle of the day.

After the pandemic and started the return to service – this was not taken back. We have requested numerous times, if possible, to re-install, providing reasons such as protection from sudden rain when the band is playing and with electrical equipment exposed to open without any immediate cover. Rain and Electricity is not a perfect combination and cannot be together. It has risk and hazardous.

This was first brought up to the head of the department of entertainment which is the Cruise Director. Then it was escalated to the Hotel Director to the Staff Captain who is in charge with the deck department and its installation until to the captain. Nothing was done even after we brought up the issue of hazard and risk . We brought it up as Seabourn encourage everyone to say something if they see something and to do something. It is a culture of Safety.

The president of Seabourn also came to visit the ship and we mentioned to him also the situation when we had the chance to talk to him during an invitation to all crew for a meeting. The president said he will look into it but also nothing has happened until today. The reason given to us by the onboard management was it is not a Seabourn standard. We voiced out that there is another ship of Seabourn

which the Seabourn Sojourn that successfully re installed the canopy during the return to service after the pandemic and why Seabourn Odyssey cannot be granted despite the reasons we brought up.

Many times, during our contract we experienced setting up band equipment and it got wet when it rains, and we have to run under the rain to cover all equipment and immediately unplug the power cable to avoid any electrocution. I even once electrocuted slightly when I touched the extension panel as it getting wet already. Rain normally happens when we set up when we were in Barbados and other ports in the Caribbean.

Management will stop the band playing and will continue after the rain even when all the equipment is wet for guest satisfaction.

Since we kept voicing out our feedback regarding safety matters, our team lost its confidence in the management and our morale went down. Due to guest satisfaction and ratings – I observed the management didn't do anything for the safety of its crew and protection of its equipment. That an event must go on regardless of the situation.

Crew satisfaction is greatly affected as management didn't observe safety essentials being brought up by its crew who are personally experiencing the situation.

Also, another experience I had was in Seabourn Pursuit this year. I had an accident and I hurt my back and was treated by the doctor and was advised to be careful not to lift heavily. I asked the management for helpers to assist my colleague in set up and striking while I am recovering.

We asked the Utility Housekeeping at night if they are willing to help and to include it in their Overtime so Entertainment can pay them 10 usd per hour. They welcome

the idea as this is also the situation on other Seabourn ships. Utility housekeeping assists in spotlight, set up and backstage when they are needed.

However, the Hotel Director didn't approve it because he said there are only three (3) HK utilities at night. However, these utilities are willing to do it as they have been doing this on other ships. Even the request to ask helpers while I'm recovering is valid – he didn't lend any assistance. For whatever other reasons aside from there being only three Utility at night, I don't know anymore. So, my colleague ends up setting the equipment on his own and strikes it late at night on his own. The equipment she was setting and striking are subwoofers with wheels that weigh 100 lbs. plus and, two speakers, a tripod, table and its stand. This is also an issue for safety as I had an incident because of lifting and now my colleague was on his own carrying everything and turning upside down the subwoofer because of its connection.